

Cluster-building action plan / D7.3

WP 7, T 7.3

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3. Introduction

Purpose

Two Circular Construction Clusters (CCC) will be set up at regional level, Brussels and Barcelona (and further regional territories) and registered in Circular Cities & Regions Initiative (CCRI). The CCC will use its network for dissemination and replication purposes, also knowledge creation and co-creation & validation activities with the sector, and at the same time in European level, for supporting CCRI activities for cities and regions in close cooperation with the CCRI Coordination and Support Office (CCRI-CSO). They will be established according to the specifications of this report in order to ensure the effective cocreation, dissemination, communication and exploitation of the project's results at a regional level and with CCRI stakeholders.

In addition, one key aspect of the clustering activities will be to liaise with regional and European policy makers and the European Commission agents to discuss the challenges of adopting systemic circular building solutions and to provide recommendations on policy and action plans. Identifying research & innovation gaps and provide inputs of the Circular System Solution intended to demonstrate will be also an objective. During the duration of these clustering, stakeholders they will support validation activities for the development of the project results and in return, training modules will be created and included in the cluster platform for their benefit.

Thanks to this close collaboration with CCRI, any results relevant to the CCRI community will be promoted also through CCRI channels and included in the knowledge repository on the CCRI website (e.g. policy briefs and recommendations produced by the project), as well as in the repository within the project's stakeholder platform that will be created as the base for the functioning of Reconstruct regional clusters. This digital stakeholder platform will support the operations of the CCCs, act as a launching pad for the project's social innovation and co-creation activities, and host the training activities and materials developed within the project in a dedicated module.

The CCC are planned to be settled up between October 2024 and November 2024, starting the engagement strategy in March 2024 and landing the first version web-based stakeholder platform in February 2025 to be tested. Until the platform is launched, the activities at regional level will be implemented outside the platform, through collaboration in other meeting platforms but recording and summarizing these actions to add them later into the repository of the platform.

SOO will support the viewpoint of methodology for co-creating the clusters and will be responsible for the coordination of activities between the two clusters' interaction in close cooperation with the CCRI-CSO. On the other side, regional institutions or organisations will lead the activities for the formation and activities during the cluster operation; being INC in the case of the Barcelona cluster and GEP and VUB for the Brussels cluster. Finally, IRIS will develop the virtual spaces and modules within the Stakeholder platform that the cluster

and its members can use. Also, the stakeholders engagement will be carried out by ICONS and the involvement of stakeholder participation in co-creation activities will be held mainly by WP6 partners to provide timely policy feedback to the CCRI-CSO regarding EU policies, among other activities defined in the Cluster Action Plan, where each partner will be in charge of the activities according to its expertise.

Considerations

This report will specify the main co-creation activities planned and internal validation needs of the project within the clustering but focusing on those that are directly outside the dissemination and communication plan or the replication plan at European level. This aspect is not object of this report, and it will be executed on the basis of a comprehensive plan for the dissemination, exploitation and communication activities; specify in *Plan of the Dissemination and Communication activities*¹ and *Plan of Exploitation activities*², of Reconstruct.

This first version of the Action Plan has been validated by the Reconstruct partners in charge of the cluster through workshops for regional activities. Once an initial group of external cluster stakeholders are involved, the next step will be communicating and agreeing with them the fundamental principles defined in this report through meetings of engagement. On the other hand, this Plan will be also agreed with the CCRI-CSO at European level, trying to identify cooperation activities, maximising synergies and knowledge exchanges, and overall, avoiding overlaps within CCRI and the Sister projects³. This validation at European level is done in a joint approach with the Dissemination and communication plan and the Replication plan.

Structure

In order to define the Cluster Action Plan, the partners identify the initial scope and objectives of the clusters and conduct regional stakeholder mapping to identify all the stakeholders that fall within this scope. Afterwards, the cluster activities are planned and cluster roles are defined. It is also essential to establish a Monitoring and Evaluation Plan to assess the success of the cluster and mitigate potential risks. The next steps after the definition of this Cluster Action Plan, would be followed by engagement activities and the organization of a series of meetings and workshops where the stakeholders will be invited to define their level of engagement and the co-creation activities they can support. After these steps, the cluster is considered set up, which will be registered at the CCRI, and the implementation of the participative activities starts, beginning with a Kick-off event.

This is the structure that has been followed in the organisation of this report, ordered by the steps followed to define the fundamental principles of the cluster, as explained in the above paragraph.

¹ Report in: <https://reconstruct-project.eu/>

² Internal Reconstruct report

³ Sister projects are EU projects under the same topic or topics within Horizon Europe Cluster 4

4. State of Art

4.1. Cluster Concept

The term cluster can be interpreted in several ways, depending on the context and its functionalities. It can also refer to groups of objects or individuals in various contexts, such as biological clusters (e.g., galaxies, cells), social clusters (e.g., communities, tribes) or technical clusters (e.g., researchers exchanging scientific information or building stakeholders with common interests).

A definition that allows us to understand the term cluster in its broadest sense in this case could be that of the pioneer author in the interpretation of the term, Porter, as follows: “A cluster is a group of interconnected enterprises and associated institutions, linked by common and complementary activities and interests, geographically close to each other.”⁴ This term is often also associated with “networks or sectoral innovation systems that do not necessarily involve the idea of geographic concentration of activity”⁵ (wider geographical scale). In the context of the building sector the cluster concept refers to the idea of bringing together different people and organizations in the construction industry and some other related sectors, such as real estate developers, builders, material manufacturers, architects, engineers, and suppliers, researchers, public administration, in a geographically close area. This could mean some benefits, such as:

- Improved communication and collaboration: clustering can help to break down barriers between different stakeholders, leading to improved collaboration.
- Knowledge sharing: clusters can act as hubs for knowledge sharing and innovation, helping to spread best practices and develop new technologies.
- Boosting the transformation: clusters, if they are made up of representatives with the capacity to act in the sector, make it possible to accelerate changes.
- Reduced costs: clustering can lead to economies of scale and reduced logistical costs for entities in the building sector.

However, it is important to keep in mind that there could be some potential drawbacks, depending on how the clusters are organised and managed, such as:

- Excessive competition: clusters could create a more competitive environment, which can be beneficial for innovation but also lead to loss of development cooperation.
- Limited scope: clustering may only be beneficial for certain types of building projects, entities and stakeholders.
- Saturation of the relational system: due to the large existence of clusters, networks, associations and groups with related interests, stakeholders may be overburdened.

⁴ Porter, M. E, On competition (inside *Clusters and Competition. New Agendas for Companies, Governments and Institutions.*). Bilbao: Ediciones Deusto, 1998.

⁵ Navarro Arancegui, M., Análisis y políticas de clusters: teoría y realidad, ESTE. Universidad de Deusto, 2003.

- Government support and leadership: clusters often require government or official support to be successful, which may not always be available.

Clusters could be classified according to the following points: a) spatial boundaries of the cluster (inter/national, regional or local), b) type of relationship between firms or sectors (interdependence or similarity), c) type of flows (of products or knowledge), d) organisations and institutions taken into consideration⁶ as well as its competitiveness.

Also, the terms “cluster” and “hub” have differences and similarities that are worth bearing in mind. Both can be used to describe organizational or geographical structures. Clusters in the construction sector often refer to geographic concentrations of interconnected businesses and/or research and development fostering collaboration and business opportunities, while hubs may represent centralized points or networks for specific functions or services within the construction industry which could be the same as those mentioned before but with no initial business direct intention. Both concepts aim to enhance efficiency, collaboration, and innovation within the sector, but they could do so in different ways.

As defined by ACCIÓ (Agency for Business Competitiveness of the Government of Catalonia, Spain), that promotes and coordinates several clusters in different sectors in Catalonia. For this agency a cluster is *“Business partnerships (a concentration of interconnected companies, organizations, and institutions) that provide a framework for the development of joint initiatives particularly in industry or other sectors within the region”*⁷. This entity has established 27 clusters that already include more than 2,700 companies and partners, and have a turnover of over 70,000 million euros. Complementary to this definition, Antonio Novo says, president of the National Federation of Innovative Business Groupings and Clusters (FENAEIC⁸) that *“the most effective clusters are those that are born as a result of the initiative of the companies themselves from the same province or autonomous region that work in the same sector or are engaged in complementary activities”*⁹.

On the other part, a business hub specifically would *“function as a business centre, as it is a workspace that allows companies to be grouped under the same paradigm or territory and where there is a synergy between brilliant ideas and sufficient investment capital to materialise projects”*¹⁰. They are transit sites that can be physical or virtual but they help in consolidating new industry sectors.¹¹

In the case of the project Reconstruct, another essential reference to bring here is the one provided by the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative – CCRI that is part of the EU Circular

⁶ Navarro Arancegui, M., Análisis y políticas de clusters: teoría y realidad, ESTE. Universidad de Deusto, 2003.

⁷Catalunya Clusters: https://www.accio.gencat.cat/web/.content/01_Serveis/clusters/Troba-el-teu-cluster/doc/cataleg-clusters.pdf

⁸ Federación Nacional de Agrupaciones Empresariales Innovadoras y Clústeres

⁹ Diputación de Granada: <https://www.granadaempresas.es/noticias/forme-cluster-innovar-junto-otras-companias/>

and Expansion Economic Journal, 2024:

[https://www.expansion.com/pymes/2017/09/06/59a96b7cca4741a6168b461c.html#:~:text=%C2%BFC%C3%B3mo%20crearlo%3F,Innovadoras%20y%20Clusters%20\(Fenaetic\).](https://www.expansion.com/pymes/2017/09/06/59a96b7cca4741a6168b461c.html#:~:text=%C2%BFC%C3%B3mo%20crearlo%3F,Innovadoras%20y%20Clusters%20(Fenaetic).)

¹⁰ <https://www.conekta.com/blog/hub-empresarial>

¹¹ <https://hablemosdeempresas.com/pymes/que-es-un-hub/>

Economy Action Plan, particularly in the area of the Horizon Europe projects; where “a territorial cluster is a socio-economic, geographical and environmental system composed of all relevant actors and including at least one public authority¹².” In particular in this initiative that also aims to increase synergies among projects and initiatives and other stakeholders, the cluster would be “ready to implement, demonstrate and facilitate the replication of at least one Circular Systemic Solution in a specific territory”.

In summary, the main characteristics of the different cluster and hub conceptions, which are of interest for this project to define the regional clusters that they will be settled up, are presented in the following graph:

Figure 1. Clusters concepts - source: own elaboration, Societat Orgànica.

The first line presents the business cluster usual concept aimed at strengthening the company's competitiveness by developing key skills, technologies and networked relationships between manufacturers, customers and suppliers. The cluster can bring together different actors from different sub-sectors of the construction industry, who usually organise themselves without the involvement of the public administration. Participation requires a fee and is usually not financially supported by the public sector.

The second line summarises another cluster concept that takes some references and characteristics from the hub concept. It is inspired in the CCRI definitions and its objective is to demonstrate and facilitate the replication of at least one Circular Systemic Solution in a specific territory. The stakeholders and entities involved can be similar to the case of clusters focused on business development although, given the research & development driven character and including public initiatives and public funding, their participation is free of charge. Another important difference is that the beneficiaries of the cluster's actions are not only the cluster members all the entities from the building sector who are interested in increasing the circularity of resource management.

¹² CCRI website, European Comission: <https://circular-cities-and-regions.ec.europa.eu/>

The concept adopted combines cluster and hub characteristics, creating a centre of activity and a network at the regional level. It is a workspace that allows stakeholders and entities to be grouped under the same circular economy paradigm and territory (Barcelona and Brussels regions in the case of this project) where there is a synergy between innovative knowledge and financial support capable to materialise projects and drive sector transformation.

The Reconstruct clusters will not be what is usually understood as business centres, but they will still help to improve competitiveness and development of the sector. They will provide and demonstrate circular technical solutions for increased resource efficiency, reduced raw material extraction and waste generation, and increased reuse and recycling. All this means improvements in costs, productivity and reducing environmental impacts for entities in the building sector that are interested in participating in the cluster and, ultimately, applying the results of the project, trying to get to the industry.

4.2. Cluster fundamental principles and steps

Generally speaking, a successful building sector cluster involves establishing a collaborative environment among the related entities. By developing a structured and collaborative cluster, stakeholders can enhance innovation, competitiveness, and sustainability. Successful clusters often serve as catalysts for economic development and the transformation of the sector.

In the creation of a cluster, it is essential to define its fundamental principles and action plan. The development of these concepts should include the definition of the vision and mission, the objectives to be achieved, the stakeholders to be convened, the strategic steps to be taken, the roles of the participants, the procedures to be followed and the governance mechanisms that ensure participation and inclusion in its functioning. This concept will be called the strategic steps.

4.2.1. Fundamental principles of clusters

According to experience, the structure of a construction cluster should consider the following aspects that were considered in the definition of the Reconstruct project clusters, explained in the section below [5. Cluster Action Plan of Reconstruct](#).

Table 1: Fundamental principal of clusters

Vision, mission and objective/s
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Vision: outlines the aspirational future state or desired outcome that the cluster aims to achieve and provides a picture of what success looks like in the long term. - Mission: articulates the fundamental purpose, values, and identity of the cluster with a clear and succinct description of why the cluster exists.

- Objectives: represent the goals to be achieved through the operation of the cluster, which should be ambitious, measurable and achievable.
- Plan & time: establish a plan of the main activities or actions to be carried out in the short, medium or long term as agreed upon

Leadership, membership, governance

- Manager and Coordinator: a person or institution responsible for managing and coordinating cluster activities.
- Membership and Stakeholders: diverse representation within the specific target of the building sector or subsector covering all needed roles and profiles to achieve the objectives.
- Working groups: focus on specific aspects such as innovation, dissemination or workforce development.

Infrastructure, resources and functionality

- Physical infrastructure: meeting virtual and face to face spaces, shared facilities, and innovation hubs, to facilitate collaboration and knowledge exchange.
- Financial resources: funding for cluster initiatives and collaborative activities between the cluster and other organisations.
- Participative activities: regular meetings, workshops and networking to facilitate collaboration addressed to key challenges, best practices, and emerging trends.

Research, innovation, training

- Research and Development (R&D): boost research activities, encourage collaboration on development projects, new technology and methodologies.
- Technology transfer: facilitate the transfer of technology and knowledge among cluster members, promoting the adoption of innovative solutions.
- Skills development: implement programs for workforce development and skills training to address the evolving needs of the building sector.

Monitoring, evaluation, plan adjustment

- Performance metrics: determine key performance indicators (KPIs) to measure the success of the cluster in achieving its objectives.
- Regular evaluation: conduct regular evaluations to assess the impact of cluster initiatives and identify areas for improvement.
- Advocacy initiatives: work closely with policymakers to influence government policies that improve innovation and sustainability in the building sector.

4.2.2. Main steps in the clustering process

Creating a building sector cluster involves a systematic process that includes planning, coordination, and engagement with stakeholders like the ones previously mentioned to define jointly the agreed fundamental principles. In brief, the step-by-step process to guide the definition and the establishment of the defined clusters includes the following steps.

1. **Analysis of market:** existing clusters in operation, best practices clusters and current innovation gaps within the scope of the cluster
2. **Vision, Scope and Objectives:** to define these fundamental principles of the cluster in order to understand why this cluster is needed, for what purpose it is created and to enable the mapping of stakeholders within the scope of the cluster.
3. **Mapping and identification of companies, organisations and entities** that may be interested in participating within the scope of the cluster: identify them taking into account their geographical location, sector or industry and their common interests.
4. **Planning and coordination:** of the activities and actions to be carried out in the framework of the cluster, in order to achieve the proposed objectives.
5. **Determine governance & roles, type of collaboration and cooperation:** type of governance, membership criteria, how information, knowledge and resources will be shared to achieve common objectives.
6. **Physical or virtual infrastructure where to operate in the cluster:** meeting virtual and face to face spaces in shared facilities to facilitate this collaboration, knowledge exchange and planned activities/actions.
7. **Start to operate with the cluster:** implement actions and activities plan within this structure and space.
8. **Follow the engagement of stakeholders to strengthen the network:** as cluster activities and actions are implemented, the network of contacts and relationships between cluster members is strengthened, and it can also be strengthened with new stakeholders interested in participating in order to generate new opportunities and collaborations.
9. **Monitoring, evaluation and continuous improvement:** It is important to periodically evaluate the results and impact of the cluster's activities and actions in order to identify areas for improvement and adjust the strategy according to the results obtained¹³ as well as to look for possible future ambitions not specified at the beginning.

This report is organised in the same step-by-step structure to facilitate its comprehension.

¹³ <https://nersasl.com/cluster/>

4.3 Existing local clusters

It has been deemed necessary to analyze existing clusters at the regional and even national level in order to learn about what proposals are being implemented and identify which are the research & innovation gaps that are not being addressed by the current clusters and where therefore, the Reconstruct clusters could add value in and make specific contributions. Also, this analysis of existing clusters under the scope of circular economy in the building sector and on the management of materials related with the project, could serve to discover if the cluster context is oversaturated, try to propose cluster initiatives that bring together some of the most stimulating initiatives and interconnect them to add value.

Reconstruct cluster contributions could be made through the constitution of a new relational system to be established among the sector's stakeholders and entities, by collaborating with existing clusters or by combining both modalities. Whether it eventually becomes one type of cluster or the other, there is always the intention to establish collaborative relationships with the clusters, hubs and other organizations that are currently operating.

In any case, what is needed is to implement, demonstrate and facilitate the replication of Circular Systemic Solutions developed in the project, in a specific territory. As mentioned above, this can be done through one or more of the following relational system modalities:

- Cluster: is a socio-economic system, regionally determined, composed of all relevant actors and including at least one public authority.
- Hub: is the effective center of an activity, region, or network that also can work in the same sense and with similar capabilities as the cluster.
- Other forms of organization and communication between stakeholders and sector entities with similar capabilities.

The study of the existing organizations in the territories of Barcelona and Brussels, as they are the pilot areas of the project, also seeks to detect what initiatives are being carried out, what their strategic plans are like, which level of activity is running out (active organization, in formation, temporarily deactivated, that has ended...). This information will help to define the project proposals and to avoid overlapping or redundancies with activities already underway (but to join them). The idea is to collaborate with stakeholders and entities that share the objectives of the circular economy that this study will help to detect and contact.

As the need to manage resources in a circular way has a transversal character, different organizations in the sector dedicated to construction, materials, waste, innovation, training, etc., will be taken into account (even if they have not expressly declared their interest in the circular economy).

The key elements that have been analysed in each existing cluster or organisation on circular economy in the building sector attempts to answer our initial questions about:

- Vision, mission, objectives
- Activities, working plans, management

- Territorial or national scope
- Functional limitations
- Type of participants and number (all entities and companies, SME, microenterprises, etc.) – identify stakeholders that can also contribute within Reconstruct.
- Thematic field (circular economy, building technology, waste management...)
- Relationships among other organisations and topic relation with Reconstruct

In this research, the main aspects that have been analysed by region and in EU level in each cluster or organization are:

- General information: name, type, platform, lead partner
- Participants: type of stakeholders, number of members
- Mission: objectives, scope
- Way of working: type of activities, action examples, communication
- Linkage: engagement, networking, relationships
- Reconstruct specific interest related

4.2.3. Barcelona

This section presents the clusters, hubs and other organizations that are considered most relevant according to the criteria defined in the previous section. The search is focused on the metropolitan area of Barcelona, although cases from other parts of Catalonia and the rest of Spain are included.

The list is not exhaustive but demonstrative, the cases presented have been selected from a larger set based on their representativeness by thematic area, degree of presence in the sector and specific interest for the Reconstruct project.

They are listed below according to the aspects explained above:

Name: Clúster MAV - Clúster de Materials Avanzats de Catalunya

Type: cluster

Platform: <https://www.clustermav.com/>

Stakeholders type: from raw material manufacturers in biopolymers, metallic materials, composites, plastics, textiles, ceramics and glass to processors, producers and end users

Number of stakeholders: 60+

Stakeholders involved: HP, Rimsa, Universitat de Girona, CIM UPC, Fundació Eurecat, IREC, etc.

Objectives: to become the preeminent cluster in materials and technologies and the leading problem solver for sectors in which materials play a key role by bringing businesses and knowledge together

Scope: territorial

Type of activities implemented: advanced materials and their technologies

Example of activity: drive the circular economy model and the green transition: Update on the state of the art, key trends and new developments in the circular economy. Search for synergies between partners to implement innovative sustainability projects. Promote the circular economy model among partners and society as a whole. Transfer knowledge about new technologies which enable the implementation of the circular economy. Engage with nationwide circular economy projects and initiatives.

Communication channels: <https://twitter.com/clustermav>,
<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC9zhfOjBSmGxj77qN94Puyw>,
<https://www.linkedin.com/company/cluster-de-materials-avancats-de-catalunya/>

Name: CSIM - Clúster de serveis immobiliaris

Type: Cluster

Platform: <https://csim.es/>

Stakeholders type: Construction and rehabilitation; Electrical marketing company; real estate portal; facility management; digital solutions; Capital management, home automation solutions, temporary rental management; Insurance; Water supply and cleaning; elevators; Bank; Farm administrator; Architecture; University and; Others.

Number of stakeholders: 46

Objectives: To transform real estate services. Promote the modeling of innovative and adaptive responses; Promote modeling traffic in the implementation of specific formulas; Promote entrepreneurship and innovation. Produce knowledge and value.

Type of activities implemented: CSIM meetings; Strategic visits; Training – CSIM School; Innovation workshops; Participation in real estate events; #InmoDate strategic session; CSIM days; Strategic sessions; CSIM executive commissions.

Communication channels: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/cluster-csim/>,
https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCs3NLvh7qRFjCT6n5_F1GBA, <https://twitter.com/CSIMcluster>

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Name: Eraikune - Construction Cluster of the Basque Country

Type: Cluster

Platform: <http://www.eraikune.com/>

Stakeholders type: Professional associations and colleges; CCTT, OCT and LAB, Training Centers and Universities; Materials and manufacturers; Promotion, construction and rehabilitation; Related technical services; public company; Valorization and circular economy

Number of stakeholders: 128

Objectives: The vision of Eraikune is to be the reference cluster within the construction industry, being the engine of economic, social and territorial transformation of the Basque Country (Spain).

Scope: 1) Energy efficiency and indoor air quality; 2) Building 4.0; 3) Smart cities and smart buildings; 4) Sustainability and circular economy; 5) Sustainable urban development; 6) New markets

Type of activities implemented: Support in planning, management and administration of projects, as well as the task of processing applications for financing and economic subsidies.

Example of activity: Technological surveillance work, search for new business lines and diversification strategies, organization of Business to Business (B2B) meetings, technical seminars that facilitate collaborative business opportunities.

Communication channels: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/eraikune/>, <https://www.instagram.com/eraikune/>, <https://profile.clustercollaboration.eu/profile/cluster-organisation/d9ef14ed-c4b8-46b3-8291-e17f413a1fc2>

Name: Cluster Edificació

Type: Cluster

Platform: <https://clusteredificacion.com/>

Stakeholders type: corporate organisation, property developers, real estate companies, university, producers/distributors of materials, construction firms, insurance company

Objectives: The Building Cluster has several strategic axes for the development and implementation of innovative processes and products in different areas of the sector. All of this will improve the competitiveness of the associated companies and their international projection and visibility.

Number of stakeholders: 90+

Stakeholders involved: ASPRIMA, KRONOS, UPM, Saint Gobain, ARPADA, ASEFA, etc.

Objectives: information on the latest trends in R+D+I, promotes innovation + training

Scope: Territorial, open to the participation of companies and organisations active in the buildings value chain

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Name: CEEC - Clúster d'Energia Eficient de Catalunya

Type: Technology, research, institutional, regulatory, industrial, information and business

CEEC
Clúster d'Eficiència
Energètica de Catalunya

Platform: <https://www.clusterenergia.cat/>

Stakeholders type: Companies and entities

Stakeholders involved: Schneider Electric, Generalitat de Catalunya, b_TEC, COMSA, ISTEM, Simon, etc.

Objectives: Strengthen the energy efficient sector and achieve projection exterior.

Scope: Territorial

Name: Catalunya Circular. El Observatorio de Economía Circular

Type: Hub

Lead partner: Generalitat de Catalunya

Scope: Territorial

Platform:

https://mediambient.gencat.cat/ca/05_ambits_dactuacio/empresa_i_produccio_sostenible/economia_verda/catalunya_circular

Stakeholders type: corporate organisations, property developers, real estate companies, university, producers/distributors of materials, construction firms, insurance company

Objectives: Innovation hub and meeting point for companies and institutions that provide solutions and strategies to consolidate the circular economy in Catalonia.

Type of activities implemented: Congress, dissemination, contests

Example of activity: -

Name: Barcelona Centre de Disseny

Type: Design

Platform: <https://www.bcd.es/en/mission/>

**Barcelona
centre
de Disseny**

Stakeholders type: Companies and Entities, Universities and Innovation centres

Number of stakeholders: 129

Stakeholders involved: UIC Barcelona, RMIT, HP, Escofet, etc.

Objectives: To give design the importance it had in other European cities. Innovation and sustainability of organizations, Support for creative entrepreneurship, Promotion of the Barcelona brand, Challenges of society and the United Nations sustainable development goals, the 2030 Agenda.

Scope: Territorial

Type of activities implemented: In order to promote creative talent and corporate entrepreneurship, they offer inspiring programs for the materialization of ideas and generation and acceleration of new projects, from the perspective of design thinking, and with the collaboration of professionals from the field of innovation and design, sustainability and entrepreneurship.

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Example of activity: Workshops, exhibitions

Related with reconstruct: The Circular Economy presents a new economic and social model with the aim of producing and consuming in a more responsible and efficient manner. In Barcelona Design centre, we promote design as one of the main drivers to integrate the circular economy into business models, production processes and the habits of society in general. We do this through participation in international cooperation projects, and through the implementation of local initiatives.

Name: Going Circular Hub

Type: hub

Platform: <https://goingcircularhub.com/>

Stakeholders type: start-up companies, corporations, research centres and universities

Leader: it is an initiative promoted by GELLIFY

Number of stakeholders: 18+

Stakeholders involved: Sorigué, Fira Barcelona, ACCIÓ, Acciona, Corbion, Cosentino, Unilever, OW, Sacyr, Endesa, Suez, etc.

Objectives: The first Spanish ecosystem where start-up companies, corporations, research centres and universities that want to develop circular economy projects can share information, experiences and cooperate to create innovative solutions.

Scope: Regional

Type of activities implemented: networking, communication, events, specific development projects.

Example of activity: (blog) <https://goingcircularhub.com/blog/>

Related with reconstruct: this hub shares the objective of the development and implementation of the circular economy in construction.

4.2.4. Brussels

In this section, similar to the previous one, clusters, hubs and other relevant organizations are presented. The search is focused on the Brussels Capital Region, although cases from other parts of Belgium and some European-wide are also included.

The list is not exhaustive but demonstrative, the cases presented have been selected from a broader set based on their representativeness by thematic area, degree of presence in the sector and specific interest for the Reconstruct project.

Name: ecobuild.brussels

Type: cluster

Platform: <https://ecobuild.brussels/en/cluster/>

Stakeholders type: federations & representative bodies, promotion, training & support organizations and universities, institutes & research centres.

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Leader: The Supervisory Committee is the cluster's monitoring body.

Number of stakeholders: 26

Stakeholders involved: ARIB, BATICREA, Brussels Environment, BUILDWISE, CASABLANCO, CERAA, Construcity.Brussels, VUB...

Objectives: to develop and structure the offer in sustainable construction to help companies become more competitive and win new markets. Its action focuses on the renovation of the building stock and on the circular aspects of construction.

Scope: Regional (Brussels Capital Region)

Type of activities implemented: Bring together players in the construction sector to connect them, foster collaborations and catalyse new public or private opportunities. Organize a monitoring of innovative practices, facilitate the sharing of this practices within the sector and inspire new sustainable business models. Internationalising.

Example of activity: Internationalising. Invitation in international missions, study trips and fairs. Putting in contact with potential partners or customers via the network of economic and commercial advisers. Access to European funding programs.

Communication channels: <https://www.facebook.com/ecobuild.brussels>
<https://www.instagram.com/ecobuild.brussels/> , <https://www.linkedin.com/company/ecobuild-brussels/>

Related with reconstruct: The objectives and scope of work are practically the same.

Name: Circulair Betonakkoord Vlaanderen

Type: cluster

Platform: <https://www.betonakkoord-vlaanderen.be/>

Stakeholders type: Cement and concrete companies, building associations.

Number of stakeholders: 80+

Stakeholders involved: Embuild, GBV, Fedbeton, Buildwise and VSOR (main partners)

Objectives: with the project "Circular concrete: towards a concrete agreement for Flanders" this organisation is taking the next step and further establishing itself as a reliable partner in achieving these objectives

Scope: Regional (Flanders)

Type of activities implemented: networking, sharing knowledge, events organisation,

Example of activity: Webinar Flemish Concrete Agreement | <https://www.betonakkoord-vlaanderen.be//webinar-vlaams-betonakkoord/>

Communication channels: <https://www.betonakkoord-vlaanderen.be/>

Related with reconstruct: it focuses on the research and development of technologies applicable to concrete to increase the circular management of its resources (the same subject of the Barcelona pilot).

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Name: Embuild Flanders

Type: association

Platform: <https://www.embuildvlaanderen.be/projecten/circularair-betonakkoord-vlaanderen/>

Stakeholders type: any agent active in the construction industry, larger construction companies as well as SMEs and the self-employed.

Leader: own board of representatives

Number of stakeholders: more than 10,000

Stakeholders involved: Fedbeton, CASO, FPRG, WTCB, GBV and the Flemish Construction Confederation (main partners)

Objectives: Embuild Flanders forms a solid duo with Embuild, which is active at national level. The project is part of Flanders Circular and the targeted call circular construction economy 2020.

Scope: Regional (Flanders) - National (Belgium)

Type of activities implemented: internationalisation, digitalisation, building and renovation promotion, employment, circular construction.

Example of activity: Circular Concrete Agreement Flanders

Communication channels: <https://www.facebook.com/embuildvlaanderen/>, <https://www.linkedin.com/company/embuildvlaanderen/>, https://twitter.com/embuild_vl, <https://www.youtube.com/user/VlaamseConfederatie>

Name: Circlemade (hosted by hub.brussels, the Brussels Business Support Agency)

Type: cluster

Platform: <https://circlemade.brussels/en/circlemade/>

Stakeholders type: member companies have the circular economy in common, based on one or more of the four circular economic models (circular sourcing, better use of resources, extension of product life, reuse of resources).

Number of stakeholders: 28

Stakeholders involved: BatiTerre, BC Materials, Bel Albatros, Brussels Recycling Metal, CF2D, Just Electronic, Konligo, Oxfam, PermaFungi, R-USE Fabrik...

Objectives: it is the network of circular manufacturing companies in Brussels. Its members are innovative companies that promote a more sustainable and environmentally friendly business model by working to develop manufacturing in the city.

Scope: Regional (Brussels Capital Region)

Type of activities implemented: Circlemade facilitates the development of joint projects, in particular through cooperation and the sharing of experience between members, but also by putting them in touch with key partners.

Example of activity: Visibility. Highlight the expertise of member companies through the website.

Communication channels: <https://www.facebook.com/groups/circlemade> | <https://www.linkedin.com/showcase/circlemade-brussels/>

Related with reconstruct: The objectives are practically the same, although the sector of activity is broader in Circlemade.

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Name: BeCircular

Type: govern initiative, public program

Platform: <https://www.circulareconomy.brussels/a-propos/?lang=en>

Stakeholders type: public agencies related to circular economy

Leader: Government of the Brussels-Capital Region

Number of stakeholders: 6

Stakeholders involved: Impulse Brussels, Bruxelles Environment, Propreté Brussels, Innoviris Brussels, GO4Brussels2030 and Shifthing Economy Brussels (most of them are public agencies)

Objectives: The Brussels Regional Program for a Circular Economy (BRPCE) has three general objectives: to transform environmental objectives into economic opportunities, to relocate the economy to Brussels in order to produce locally whenever possible, reduce travel, optimise land use and create added value for Brussels inhabitants and to help create employment.

Scope: Regional (Brussels Capital Region)

Type of activities implemented: Calls for innovation projects and financial support for Construction, Resources and waste, Logistic and Retail businesses.

Example of activity: The call for projects "be circular-be brussels" is an initiative of the Brussels-Capital Region for the benefit of self-employed people and businesses.

Related with reconstruct: this initiative works on the circular economy, although with an approach and scope that encompasses the economy as a whole.

Communication channels: <https://www.facebook.com/beCircular/> | https://www.instagram.com/be_circular/?hl=fr | <https://www.linkedin.com/company/becircular/>

Name: Hubs 4 circularity

Platform: <https://www.h4c-community.eu/#form>

Stakeholders type: public and private ones from industries, regions, and cities

Leader: two consortia H4C Europe and H4C ECoP

Number of stakeholders: 50+

Stakeholders involved: CIRCE, Dechema, Covestrol, Innovation Engineering, Vito, Sintef, Strane, ACR+, Klimate+, ICLEI, Technopolis...

Objectives: Accelerating the transition to industrial symbiosis, industrial-urban symbiosis and circular economy.

Scope: Europe

Type of activities implemented: networking, sharing knowledge, communication, workshops,

Example of activity: H4C Community of Practice Webinar "Investment in large (shared) Industrial (Urban) Symbiosis infrastructures" | <https://www.h4c-community.eu/event/h4c-community-of-practice-webinar-investment-in-large-shared-industrial-urban-symbiosis-infrastructures/>

Communication channels: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/hubs4circularity-community/> | https://twitter.com/H4C_Community

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Related with reconstruct: it is a network of public and private stakeholders set up under Horizon Europe to facilitate building, scaling up and replicating of ecosystems of industrial and industrial-urban symbiosis, as well as circular economy initiatives.

4.2.5. Conclusions

This research on clusters, hubs and partnerships in the Barcelona and Brussels regions has provided answers to the questions mentioned at the beginning of this section. This work also makes it possible to establish some reasoning and some initial conclusions as to what the business and institutional fabric of the construction sector is like and what it is doing in order to gradually implement the principles of the circular economy. That is, closing the cycle of materials throughout the life cycle of buildings.

The first conclusions are presented below:

The Barcelona region presents a good number of organisations, of which those of greatest interest to the project have been presented. Most of them include among their objectives the circular management of construction resources as well as the promotion of projects for the development of soft and hard technologies.

The Brussels region has several organisations dedicated in general to the circular economy and in particular to the circular management of resources in the construction sector. There is even a cluster specifically dedicated to circularity in the cement and concrete industry, which is the predominant material of one of the project pilots. The action of the public administration is remarkable, as it promotes and integrates several of the clusters and hubs detected, and it also finances most of the development projects.

Regarding the vision, mission and objectives of most of the organisations analysed, almost all of them clearly define their commitment to the transformation or transition towards a circular economy in the construction sector. When looking deeper and analysing the type, scope and number of projects with an effective impact on the circular transformation of the sector, the results change. In some clusters, there is a lack of technology development projects, either in management or production, that would bring demonstrable impact on materials manufacturing, building construction, building maintenance and deconstruction.

Notwithstanding the above, **the number of projects carried out is significant in most cases**. Although these initiatives may be insufficient to produce important changes in the sector, at least at the speed needed to meet the environmental objectives of the European Union, they are an effective testimony and an indicative reference in terms of its replicability and scalability.

The level of activity of the organizations is intense and the degree of maturity achieved seems to indicate that a certain consolidation has been reached. Most of the clusters, hubs and associations have been operating continuously for 5 or more years and have several stakeholders exceeding 10, 20 or more members. From the point of view of their integration of the circular economy, they could be divided into two types: old organizations that have

partially or totally adopted these objectives (E.g.: Embuild in the Brussels region) and new organizations that have been created from the objective of circular resource management (E.g.: Catalunya circular in the Barcelona region).

Certain **clusters and hubs studied are strategic for Reconstruct**, given their geographical scope, relationship with the construction sector, circularity objectives, types of stakeholders and partners, projects under development and openness to collaboration. On the other hand, as part of Work Package 7, a mapping of stakeholders has been carried out, which is complemented by the study of organizations presented here as part of Work Package 4. Between both studies and interactions carried out, there is a sufficient base of agents and entities to establish the collaborations foreseen for the development of the project.

It has also been detected that **the activities of presentation, transfer, interaction, validation and communication that the Reconstruct project proposes to carry out could be a good complement for most organizations**. These activities, especially those related to the generation of technology and knowledge applicable to the sector, can help clusters, hubs and associations to meet the goals and purposes set forth in their protocols, projects and communication actions.

4.3. The Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI)

Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI) is an initiative that is part of the Circular Economy 2020 Action Plan and is focused on the implementation of the circular economy in Europe through the promotion, solutions demonstration and comprehensive assistance of circularity at local and regional level over the life cycle. It is a multi-stakeholder collaboration and support scheme funded by the European Commission to help achieve the 2050 climate neutrality target set out in the European Green Deal. Therefore, is an essential initiative to take into the account in the Reconstruct Cluster Action Plan both because of the large number of stakeholders involved with the same target as Reconstruct and because of the active functioning of the initiative, which provides interesting proposals, workshops and events that would help in developing the project and its further EU level dissemination¹⁴ and contribution.

The initiative provides knowledge sharing, technical and financial support to *stakeholders across Europe's cities and regions, including regional and local authorities, industry representatives, research and technology organisations and civil society*¹⁵ and looks for research and innovation gaps and, inputs of policy recommendations to be transferred to the Governance level of the European Commission.

¹⁴ The strategy of communication and dissemination is developed in Plan of the Dissemination and Communication activities - 1st version/D7.2

¹⁵ CCRI- European Commission: <https://circular-cities-and-regions.ec.europa.eu/about>

4.3.1. Objectives

The objectives of the CCRI are to increase synergies between projects and initiatives, disseminate relevant knowledge and lessons learned, and give greater visibility to replicable best practices, as well as to support and offer concrete solutions to help cities, regions and other stakeholders find a Circular Systemic Solution (CSS) that suits their own needs, an objective shared across the clusters that will be set up in the Reconstruct project. The initiative addresses different levels of approach in achieving circularity such as economic sectors, value chains and services.

In order to put this into practice, the CCRI Coordination and Support Office has set up four Thematic Working Groups (TWGs). They discuss and exchange practical solutions for implementing Circular Systemic Solutions (CSS) in European cities and regions. These four thematic groups are Circular Construction Buildings, Circular Resource Management, Circular Bioeconomy and Circular Industries and Industrial Symbiosis, as shown in the diagram below and are composed by the four different levels of CCRI stakeholders that are specifically interested in each of these groups. Reconstruct project participates in the TWG Circular Construction and Buildings, providing Circular Systemic Solutions (CSS) to be applied and collaborating in generating more knowledge and policy recommendations, among others, jointly with the *Sister Projects* (Circ-Boost and Woodcircles).¹⁶

Figure 2. CCRI Thematic Working Groups composition - source: own elaboration, Societat Orgànica.

¹⁶ The Sister Projects are three CCRI Projects that are under the same topic of cluster 4 and we will work together in the similar objectives to contribute to the broader goals of the CCRI. The three projects are Circ-Boost, Reconstruct and Woodcircles. These projects are explained in the section [4.4.3. Sister Projects](#).

The CCRI TWGs function as "laboratories" that facilitate the application, learning and validation of the circular solutions developed by each project on specific themes and sectors and their replicability also outside the CCRI. These TWGs facilitate synergies among value chain stakeholders for further cooperation in the future. The main outcomes of these workshops are as follows:

- Discover the main challenges, barriers and opportunities for implementing the specific CSS.
- Knowledge and tools on technical, regulatory, socio-economic aspects at different local and regional scale
- Catalogue of concrete solutions and replicable good practices
- Policy recommendations and potential R&I gaps of each sector/topic

In these workshops, regular meetings are held approximately every 6 months in which the Reconstruct project participates. In these sessions, the project participates in a bidirectional way, helping the other stakeholders to validate their solutions and providing knowledge support as well as disseminating the solutions developed within the project to the other stakeholders, objectives pursued in the Reconstruct regional clusters (objective 1, 2 and 4 explained in the section [5.2.Objectives in the cluster](#)).

4.3.2. Members

The CCRI stakeholders consist of four different groups of members according to their stakeholder type and the role they play within the initiative, namely Pilots, Fellows, CCRI Projects and Associated Partners, under the coordination of the CCRI Coordination and Support Office (CCRI-CSO). The main relationships between them in summary is shown in the following scheme, although in some cases there is broader collaboration in all areas.

Figure 3. CCRI members main relations - source: own elaboration, Societat Orgànica.

There are 12 Pilots and 25 Fellows selected and participating in CCRI. Both benefit from the potential collaboration, relevant information and visibility provided by the CCRI channel at European level. In particular, the pilots are cities and regions that currently already show high circularity potential and benefit from the CCRI platform by receiving tailored support to implement the developed Circular Systemic Solutions, serving as demonstration pilots. In contrast, the fellows are also composed of cities and regions plus territorial clusters that have a lower level of implementation of circular economy strategies but have a strong interest in expanding their knowledge to implement them in the near future. Their participation is focused on increasing their knowledge by the implementation of specific peer-to-peer training activities and working groups.

On the other hand, CCRI's Associate Partners are a wider group ranging from initiatives supported or managed by the European Commission to organisations, foundations or other institutions implementing projects, services and initiatives. They cooperate closely with CCRI-SO in providing and disseminating valuable inputs to the pilots and fellows, implementing CCRI activities. Also, they encourage synergies between organisations, initiatives and CCRI members with additional networking channels.

Finally, the CCRI Projects are research and innovation projects, funded by Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe, which are generating innovative knowledge, creating specific skills and

demonstrating circular systemic solutions (circular business and governance models) to be tested in the Pilots (local and regional level) and linking the CCRI to other initiatives and stakeholders. Also, they provide project development assistance services, which provide project promoters with the technical, economic and legal expertise needed for developing circular economy investments.

4.3.3. Sister Projects

The Sister Projects are CCRI Project under the same cluster 4, that is, under the same scope and related topic, which are carrying out pilots on different specific circular solutions. It consists of three projects: Reconstruct¹⁷, Circ-Boost¹⁸, Woodcircles¹⁹.

In the case of Woodcircles is a project that aims to develop circular and sustainable solutions for wood in construction, design removable connection testing their demountability and develop two new value chains for recycled wood in three pilots developed by 20 European partners across the wood construction value chain; while in the other two projects, the demonstration focuses on the realisation of demountable concrete (and other) solutions in different pilots. In the case of Circ-Boost, the five pilots will demonstrate, at large-scale, novel and integrated solutions for demolition, construction waste processing, management, and valorisation in new products and, in Reconstruct, both on-site and prefabricated concrete solutions prepared for dismantling will be tested in two pilots, with the identification of recovery and reuse routes after dismantling of the components as well as the corresponding assessments by a digital twin of the demonstrators, among others.

Therefore, due to the similarities in the testing of the circularity of the demos and assessments that will be carried out and in which a circular improvement in conventional constructions is intended, we will collaborate closely with them in the involvement of stakeholders, joint actions and not overlapping knowledge and activities. Especially in our case, with the Circ- Boost project, given that one of the pilots coincides regionally, Barcelona, in terms of dismantling, reuse and recycling and in terms of possible stakeholders. An initial collaboration has been established and the first steps have been defined, such as collaborating in a mapping of stakeholders and in joint activities with them in some cases, in order not to overlap or overload the stakeholders and, thus, to be more efficient in the development of these activities. Possibly, the stakeholder platform can be used in some activities or events with Circ-Boost, thus promoting its use and increasing its visibility.

¹⁷ Further information: <https://reconstruct-project.eu/>

¹⁸ Further information: <https://circboostproject.eu/>

¹⁹ Further information: <https://woodcircles.eu/>

5. Clusters Action Plan in Reconstruct

5.1. Strategic steps for cluster formation and operation

As explained in [4.2.2 Main steps in the clustering process](#), creating a building sector cluster involves a systematic process that includes planning, coordination, and engagement with stakeholders. The step-by-step process to guide the definition and the establishment of the Reconstruct clusters includes the following steps. This structure was followed in the co-creating meetings with the initial group of stakeholders (internally to Reconstruct) for defining the fundamental principles of the clusters and the Cluster Action Plan. The current state of task completion is also indicated.

- Analysis of existing actions plans and clusters in operation and best practices related within Reconstruct goals: task 1.0 – compiled in [4.3 Existing local clusters](#)
- Define objectives, characteristics and scope validated with the initial group of stakeholders of the initiative (partners of the consortium): task 1.0 – explained in [5.2 Objectives in the cluster](#)
- Resources and funding: inside Reconstruct project until Month May 2027: task 1.0 – explained in [5.6 Stakeholder platform](#) / after Reconstruct project some considerations have been studied in [5.3 Consideration on the scope and limits of the cluster](#)
- Conduct stakeholder analysis: task 1.0 – detailed in [5.4 Stakeholder Mapping](#)
- Determine stakeholders mapping within the scope defined in the clusters: task 1.0 (first version both in Spain and Belgium validated with the consortium) - listed in [5.4 Stakeholder Mapping](#)
- Determine governance & roles: task 0.9 (initial assumptions with only consortium partners) – explained in [5.5 Roles](#). This will be extended with external stakeholders if needed when the establishment of the cluster.
- Develop membership criteria: task 0.5, in process – further explanations in [5.3.2 Stakeholders type](#)
- Engage key stakeholders (including policymakers): task 0.0, programmed by ICONS in *Social Innovation & Circular Construction D6.1*
- Create a stakeholder platform for virtual infrastructure: task 0.2, in process by IRIS – further explanation in [5.6 Stakeholder Platform](#)
- Test with stakeholders involved the Stakeholder platform once created: task 0.0, programmed by SO
- Develop and plan participating activities: task 0.8, in process – current activities programmed indicated in [5.7. Planning activities](#)
- Share training modules, exploitation packs and other collaborative information: task 0.0, programmed by ITEC, ICONS and task leaders – further explanation in [5.7 Planning activities](#)
- Kick-off and establish working groups, to validate with stakeholders involved (internal and external to Reconstruct) the fundamental principles defined in this document

through engagement activities and organization of a series of meetings: task 0.0, programmed once an initial group of stakeholders is engaged with the cluster.

- Settle up the cluster and register to CCRI: task 0.2, in process – by SOO
- Monitor, evaluate and adjustment: task 0.0, programmed once the cluster is settled up and operating – monitoring and evaluation plan programmed is explained in [6. Monitoring and evaluation of the Cluster Action Plan](#)
- Sustain, grow and evolve (future ambitions and running the cluster beyond the project): task 0.0.

5.1.1. Timeline for cluster establishment and operation

In summary, the steps for setting up the cluster and its functioning successfully are outlined temporarily in the figure 4, being an estimation. They can also be explored in this [Miro Board](#). The different actions to be conducted are divided into four main actions:

1. stakeholder involvement,
2. establishment of the clusters,
3. development of the digital platform and
4. some of the main activities to be conducted withing the clusters, including events to organise and others to participate, validation & exploitaton of the results of the project tasks and the development of the training material/replication packs to be incorporated into the platform.

A potential risk was detected when developing the timeline of actions to be carried out for the establishment and then the operation of the clusters, to be managed properly once predicted.

In figure 4, it can be seen that several steps depend on each other for the final success of the cluster creation. In order to have a solid progression, it is essential to map the stakeholders to be involved while defining the scope and objectives of the clusters, in order to understand the context of each region and the possible limitations of the types of actors. Once the mapping is done, it is necessary to draw up an engagement plan and start contacting the stakeholders in order to form at least an initial stakeholder group that will start participating in the co-creation sessions necessary to agree the fundamental principles defined in this Action Plan and roles and working groups with external stakeholders²⁰, to set up the clusters.

²⁰ External stakeholders from Reconstruct project consortium partners

Figure 4. Timeline for cluster establishment and operation - source: own elaboration, Societat Orgànica

The cluster should be formed around September 2024 and thereafter start to operate (co-creation, events) between this initial group of stakeholders but, for this, it is necessary to have started to develop the digital platform that should serve for the cluster stakeholders to interoperate easily. Hence, once a group of at least 20 people have been engaged into the cluster, they will be able to start registering and testing the first version of the platform, detecting possible errors or lack of functions to be incorporated until a properly operational platform is finalised. From April 2025 onwards, the platform has to function independently and self-sufficiently, where the rest of the members interested in forming part of the cluster who have been gradually contacted outside this initial group can register and become part of the cluster as well, until reaching at least the minimum of 40 participants (KPI required, see [6.1. Monitoring and adjustment of the Cluster Action Plan development](#)). There is a potential risk in the formation of the cluster if the stakeholders are not contacted on time and the finalisation of the platform is delayed.

A risky step can be detected in the graph during December 2025 where, in principle, the coordination supervised from work package 7 by SOO ends and the cluster begins to run under the operation and self-coordination of each of the partners of the consortium and some stakeholder of the platform interested in having a more active role in the future (previously agreed by the consortium). To reduce the risks of lack of coordination among the consortium, self-guides for each function of the platform and manuals on how the coordination and roles of reduced so that they can operate individually but in a coordinated manner without a supervising partner. In addition, a progressive transfer of independence of functions without coordination will start during the months October 2025 to December 2025 and, although not initially scheduled, quarterly sessions will be organised between all task leaders and WP7, to plan overall actions, solve possible problems for the next three months and monitor the progress/success of the clusters. A last step could consist of transferring the cluster and platform coordination one month before the end of the project, to stakeholder(s) willing

to continue the initiative beyond the end of the project and with the same philosophy of Reconstruct.

Finally, for the platform to be successful and to achieve the KPI of 200 platform interactions, it must host content of interest according to the scope of the cluster, such as training modules, workshops organised by Reconstruct (results, validations) or by the stakeholders themselves, openlabs in the demos built and also must promote events with/of the CCRI and cluster members. Therefore, internal coordination of content creation is essential. For one side, the main results of the project work packages should be incorporated in a training module once the WP is finalised. On the other, it is planned to propose activities from the different consortium partners according to the progress of the project. At European level, coordination with CCRI-SO and Sister Projects will be also crucial for the promotion of other content of interest. If this is not the case, the exploitation of the platform may fail.

The first two training modules are scheduled for completion in September 2024 and January 2025, just when the platform is ready to go live. This will provide the platform with some initial content of the first results of the project and the second Open-lab in Brussels demo (which will be under construction by then). The other modules will be feeding the training programme in time when the results are reached in the WP. In the meanwhile, the tasks validation, co-creation sessions, events or other activities that could be implemented, will occur outside the platform and the cluster. This fact could be a limitation in terms of contacting stakeholder and share content/sessions without uploading to the platform.

Summary sessions or content created outside the initial cluster will be incorporate in the platform once it is created. The first Open-lab in Brussels, for example, it is plan to be organised around Winter of 2024, when the cluster is already settle up but the platform is still under development. A limitation could be the form to contact and engage them or distribute materials without an operating platform.

When planning the development of training modules and packs for the exploitation of results, we have tried to incorporate their development immediately after the completion of a work package (and their results obtained). The events to be held during the project at European level are explained in the Communication and Dissemination Plan, being, among others, 3 big events at European level and 3 openlabs in each demo as well as the participation in the ECESP²¹ Annual Conference (CCRI relevant member) promoting Reconstruct and TWG-CCRI events held biannually. Efforts have been made to match the events to be organised with planned project consortium meetings in order to facilitate partners' visit to the demos or other regional events at place. These events shown here are a proposal that still has not been validated with participants, and should be taken as such.

Below are shown the foundational principles of the clusters defined by the initial group of stakeholders internal to the Reconstruct project.

²¹ European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform

5.2. Objectives of the cluster

Objective/s and scope

- **Vision:** Circular transition by demonstrating and applying Circular Systemic Solutions
- **Objectives:** Generate knowledge, Stakeholders participation, co-creation & validation, Support other initiatives and events, Communication & dissemination of the outcomes (regional level) and Results exploitation.

The objectives will be the same in both regional clusters established in Barcelona and Brussels (but extended to the region) although the scope will not end up being identical due to the different context of stakeholders. These goals are divided into five, three core objectives and two crosscutting, and they will be pursued at both regional (cluster) and European (CCRI) level, which requires a different mapping of key stakeholders at both scales and the adaptation of some of the materials created, shared or disseminated. We also specifies the tasks to which they relate within the project in the following list:

- Core: Generate knowledge (all the tasks but mainly T7.6)
- Core: Stakeholders participation, co-creation & validation (all tasks but mainly WP6)
- Core: Support other initiatives, events and social media campaigns (WP7)
- Crosscutting: Communication & dissemination (T7.3 & T7.4)
- Crosscutting: Results replication & exploitation (T7.3 & T7.5 & all)

Figure 5. Relation between the Cluster objectives - source: own elaboration, Societat Orgànica

Knowledge generation will be developed inside the Reconstruct project, but also through the stakeholders engagement sessions in cluster activities, leading to training modules, info-packs, scientific publications or other outcomes providing knowledge on Circular Systemic Solutions (CCS). It would also be generated knowledge for the cluster Knowledge will also be generated by participating in other events outside the Reconstruct, of CCRI or clusters members, and promoting best practices in the field. This knowledge and initiatives will be

disseminated to the cluster and CCRI and also through other channels outside the scope of this report²². By this dissemination and also through participative sessions such as events or one-to-one meetings, the results exploitation can be carried out in order to be transferred to policies, to achieve funding for marketising the components developed (stakeholders of the cluster) or to promote the adoption of the methodologies developed within the project.

Furthermore, the relationships between the objectives at regional cluster level and European CCRI & sister project level are shown in the graph below.

Figure 6. Cluster objectives within Reconstruct - source: own elaboration, Societat Orgànica

As visible in the figure above, both communication and dissemination and the promotion of other initiatives are carried out in both directions between regional clusters and the CCRI members (and sister projects). Therefore, the coordination and planning between the regional clusters and the CCRI will be essential not to overlap and to collaborate in joint events to pool forces and not overload with duplicate information. It is essential to involve clusters in co-creation and validation activities, which will also produce useful knowledge. This knowledge will feed into the Reconstruct training modules included in the Stakeholder Platform or the generation of other content related to CCRI's objective of demonstrating Circular Systemic Solutions or of interest to the cluster's target audience. This knowledge generation will be returned to the cluster transformed into relevant and proper materials like training modules and, at the same time, it will be adapted, disseminated and distributed to

²² Included in Dissemination and Communication Plan_First version/D7.2 in <https://reconstruct-project.eu/>

the European level (including CCRI) in line with the Communication and Dissemination Plan, for greater visibility. These events, webinars and participation in other external initiatives will generate knowledge for the regional cluster. Furthermore, once the outcomes of the project have been achieved, they will be exploited. This relationship will be external, from the Reconstruct project to the clusters and the CCRI as explained before.

5.2.1. Generate knowledge

Knowledge generation is mainly produced through the creation of various training modules developed by project partners from the project results that support the demonstration of Circular Systemic Solutions²³ and are designed to steer professionals through all the common challenges faced in circular construction. Knowledge will also be generated outside of these formal training modules, be it specific content from other project outputs, those derived from the participation of stakeholders in co-creation sessions, from participation in events, webinars and workshops jointly with CCRI or cluster members outside Reconstruct or from the promotion of best practices in the field such as other Circular Systemic solutions demonstrated in other CCRI projects. These materials will be adapted from regional level to the European level to be disseminated in proper manner and based on each target audience.

In particular, the training modules will be based on the materials developed inside the Reconstruct Work Packages (like handbooks, guidelines, video clips, designs or test results, methodologies and assessments) that highlight the main outputs of selected task together with supporting documentation (thematic meetings) for easy comprehension. From these materials, a series of "knowledge clips" or "information pills" will be created, either through webinars, experts interviews, tutorials or microlearning materials that will be recorded and subsequently organised into a complete training course, divided into modules on the topics that are consistently encountered and that are dealt within each WP. Along with these thematic recordings, support training material will be provided to complement the information covered in each module.

The training programme divided into modules and its evaluation (questionnaires, gamification activities) will be defined within T7.6 once the expected results of each task are analysed and the interests of each target group are identified (validated by the cluster stakeholders and project partners). This task will be led by ITEC although all project partners will contribute by generating and delivering training material and adapting the materials to both levels (local and EU), depending on their expertise and role.

Due to the distribution by modules and knowledge clips within them, the adaptability to different profiles of key professionals within the circular transition (either by role or background) included in the clusters is facilitated. The training modules and other training

²³ "A circular systemic solution is defined as demonstration project for deploying a circular and climate-neutral economy at urban and/or regional scale, involving key stakeholders and, ideally, addressing more than one product value chain" - <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/horizon-cl6-2023-circbio-02-1-two-stage>

materials derived from the external participation will be available at regional level on the stakeholder platform of both Reconstruct clusters, in a dedicated module in the platform for this Training programme. As explained above, they will also be adapted at European level (contents and language) in order to integrate them in a wider dissemination and communication strategy²⁴ developed by ICONS and shared with the CCRI stakeholders.

Information outside the training modules will be generated through outputs outside the scope of the training modules or derived from events, webinars, workshops or openlabs carried out within the stakeholder participation sessions, which are explained in the following section [5.4.2 Stakeholders participation, co-creation & validation](#). It is still to be defined where it will be hosted within the platform, outside the dedicated training module.

5.2.2. Stakeholders participation, co-creation & validation

The activities within the cluster related with stakeholder participation consist of two types of sessions and both will allow to achieve Reconstruct project objectives at different levels: task, Work Package or general level, being this project level influential in the objectives of the TWG of the CCRI in which Reconstruct participates.

Figure 7. Level Objectives - source: own elaboration, Societat Orgànica

The first type are the stakeholder participation and co-creation activities sessions that will serve to provide timely policy feedback to the CCRI-CSO regarding EU policies, and is related mainly with WP6 of Reconstruct but also WP3/4 & 5. They will also aim to identify research and innovation gaps and to fill these gaps through training modules (T7.6) and events. These sessions are in the level of Project goals (fig.10). The ultimate goal is to discover how to facilitate the transition from business as usual to new circular practices through the discussion of the four main topics to achieve it: policies, technical solutions, business models and data & assesments, including experiences and feasibility in the sector. These conclusions will be transferred to the CCRI-SO and disseminated also through the CCRI stakeholders to reach the European level and are intimately related to the results pursued in the objective of [Results exploitation](#). Sessions/events should therefore be organised at two levels: participation of cluster stakeholders for the regional level and the transfer of these conclusions to the European level for consolidation with European stakeholders (which can be facilitated by the CCRI).

²⁴ Communication and dissemination plan

Figure 8. Main goal and four main topics of the stakeholder co-creation activities proposed in the clusters - source: own elaboration, VUB

On the other hand, sessions will be held with stakeholders to validate the inputs and outputs needed for the development of the tasks and WP of the project in order to incorporate the opinion of the sector and the best practices currently carried out in the field of circularity, providing project results validated by the clusters. As can be observed, these sessions are in the level of task and WP goals (fig 10). These inputs and outputs can be e.g. the joint elaboration of the state of the art of a given topic, consultation on methodologies, indicators, circular technical solutions or calculation tools, or the validation of the final designed solutions, etc.

Possible validation requirements for the inputs and outputs of each task-objective have been identified through workshops with all tasks and WP leaders, resulting in specific validation sessions or activities with a certain profile of stakeholders. Not all Reconstruct tasks will require this validation of inputs for the development of their task results, but it would be desirable, where possible, to validate the final outputs with cluster members. Such sessions are more for internal use than the co-creation sessions.

The following scheme summarises some of the activities that can be carried out for the validation of the inputs or outputs involved in achieving the objective of the project task. The definition of these participative activities (validation and co-creation sessions) and their planning according to the timeframe of the project are detailed in the section [5.7.1. Cluster activities timeline](#)) and these can take the form of interviews or surveys (individual) or even workshops, events or openlabs (group), as examples.

Figure 9. Example of validation sessions of inputs and outputs desirable for the development of some tasks in Reconstruct project. - source: own elaboration, Societat Orgànica

In the figure above, all these activities are carried out across both regional clusters independently to consider both contexts. In light blue, it is indicated that the tasks may require either the direct provision of inputs through stakeholder consultation (*asking for*) as well as the validation of these inputs previously considered by the project consortium (*validation*). For example, consultation on the sources to be considered for the choice of certain inputs to conduct an LCC, the existing methodologies on which to base such a calculation or in the design of the experiments to be performed. Although for the outputs obtained in the tasks, stakeholder participation will be essentially for the validation of these results (*validation*), prior consultations (*finding for*) may also be required, such as asking about the type of outputs expected and useful for the sector, for example, the consultation on what data to include in the materials passports so that it is useful for the different actors in the value chain. Within the dark blue outlined box, ways to perform such queries or validations are identified as examples, which will be defined in each case, depending on the

intention of the query and the agreement/availability with the stakeholders of the cluster and consortium.

Although ultimately the objective pursued by both types of stakeholder sessions is the same: consultation and validation of the results by the sector and experts, the sessions executed for this purpose will be of different types: co-creation sessions, which are more participatory, deal with broader questions and pursue recommendations and conclusions on a larger scale, and direct validation-consultation sessions, which are dedicated to a specific, smaller-scale topic, directly related to the process and internal results of the project (and necessary for the discussions of the first sessions in some of the cases). The definition of these participative activities and their planning according to the timeframe of the project is indicated in section [5.7 Planning activities](#) & [5.7.1 Cluster activities timeline](#) and can range from interviews or surveys to workshops, events or openlabs, among other examples. These activities will also result in knowledge generation and will be included in the stakeholder platform as indicated in the previous section, through recordings or reports of results.

5.2.3. Promote other initiatives, events and social media campaigns (CCRI)

The project will regularly participate in CCRI activities – for instance the thematic working group meetings, webinars, workshops and/or biannual CCRI conferences. Similarly, the participation of the CCRI CSO in project activities will be envisaged when relevant. Moreover, other events related with Reconstruct topics (independent of the events organised by Reconstruct) like the ones conducted by CCRI members (Horizon Europe Cluster 4²⁵) or third parties specify in the CCRI calendar²⁶ will be promoted; and other interesting initiatives that provide relevant information that emerge during the course of the project from cluster stakeholders such as the *Carbonation of concrete as a CO2 sink from COP25 to COP28* webinar from Instituto Torroja²⁷ and IECA²⁸ (Spain) or *Lower carbon concretes in BS 8500:2023* event and *Developments in structural codes and standards* webinar from MPA²⁹ Concrete Centre's³⁰ (European).

To date, participation in other events and initiatives has taken place only from the Reconstruct consortium in events such as those mentioned above, but also in others with CCRI members, promoted by them, and those of the CCRI TGWs, in person and/or virtually, such as *The ECESP Annual Conference 2023: Circular Economy – from Visions to Actions (Belgium)* organised by European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform (in CCRI) that

²⁵ Events can be identified in its calendar of activities: <https://horizoneuropencpportal.eu/ncp-networks/cluster-4/calendar>

²⁶ These events can be identify in the calendar of CCRI website: <https://circular-cities-and-regions.ec.europa.eu/events> (there are updated regularly)

²⁷ The Instituto de Ciencias de la Construcción Eduardo Torroja (IETcc) is a Centre of the Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas, belonging to the Area of Science and Technology of Materials, relevant at national level (Spain) and influential in the development of data and tools for the Ministry of Construction.

²⁸ IECA is Spanish Institute of Cement and its Applications

²⁹ MPA is Mineral Products Association

³⁰ The Concrete Center is an active group that provides a wide range of events, from free CPD-accredited webinars and lectures to seminars and full-day conference programmes. Also, they have academic resources: <https://www.concretecentre.com/CPD-Events.aspx>

Reconstruct will join annually, *CCRI TWG Circular Bioeconomy: Informal session on bio-based materials* that we joined to informed us about topics of other CCRI TWG of Reconstruct or the Third party events promoted by CCRI: *Translating The EU Green Deal into Local Action*, *10th European Summit of Regions and Cities* and the *World Circular Economy Forum 2024* organized in Belgium. A social media campaign has been promoted in collaboration with the Sister projects, *Zero Waste day* (30 March), by recording a short-videos explaining circularity potential. Once the clusters have been constituted, the participation of all cluster stakeholders in these events, according to their engagement level and activity category, will also be promoted. At European level, this promotion is done through T7.4 and will not be included in the stakeholder platform. However, this stakeholder network will be used to promote their participation in EU events through Reconstruct's website and social media, which will also serve to increase the follow-up of the project and their subscription to the newsletters.

At the regional level of each cluster, local events and initiatives will be promoted within the stakeholder platform. The participation in other events from Reconstruct will also generate interesting inputs for the development of the project such as debates in the co-creation sessions with stakeholders as well as conclusions and learnings that could be derived in the generation of materials (like in training modules) for the repository of the stakeholder platform.

Social media campaigns, which are carried out at the European level, are specified in the section 5.5.2.1 Social media campaigns del Plan of the Dissemination and Communication activities - 1st version/D7.2 de Reconstruct: *"RECONSTRUCT aims to initiate at least one social media campaign each year throughout the project implementation. These campaigns may be coordinated with other initiatives related to the CCRI and in collaboration with sister projects. Social media campaigns serve the purpose of reinforcing and actively engaging the project's followers, fostering interaction with the content shared on social media platforms. These campaigns typically revolve around a specific theme or agenda and are designed to highlight particularly innovative content, setting it apart from regular posts."* These joint initiatives with the Sister Projects are not covered by the regional Cluster Action Plan, but are covered by the european clustering of the Reconstruct project and the Sister Projects.

5.2.4. Communication & dissemination

Although this objective can be complemented with the previous one, *promote other initiatives, events and social media campaigns*, this objective tries to communicate and disseminate directly the outcomes and progress of the cluster as well as the relevant knowledge generated in the project, including training modules and co-creation sessions of the cluster stakeholders or related events. These objective is aligned with Plan of the Dissemination and Communication and in regional level, would be the Local Communication Desks (DCE) the main contact points to implement local campaigns dedicated to local stakeholders and citizens' engagement, under the coordination of the local referent. They will map and collect local content and will indicate how communication and citizen engagement activities will be tailored to the local framework.

The information to be disseminated is created within the project and the cluster and at regional level, it is communicated and disseminated through the clusters (subject of this report) and at European level, through CRR and other European bodies outside the CCRI, through the website, social media (Twitter, LinkedIn) and E-newsletter of Reconstruct as well as through other media multipliers and the partner corporate websites. The indications for the European level are explained in section 5.5 Dissemination and communication channels of the Reconstruct Plan of the Dissemination and Communication activities - 1st version/D7.2. The different formats and materials are also specified in 5.6 Dissemination and communications materials and formats and 5.7 Editorial contents of this plan. In summary, these are: communication kit, scientific and technical publications, info-packs and innovation handbook, transferring to policy briefs, webinars, local d&c desks, journalistic articles and interviews, and video production.

In the case of regional clusters, the information to be disseminated will be adapted if appropriate to the regional level and will consist only of the information generated within the cluster, which will be incorporated in specific modules of the stakeholder platform as explained in [5.2.1 Generate knowledge](#) and [5.3.2. Stakeholders participation, co-creation & validation](#). The knowledge generated (internal to the cluster such as the co-creation of policy briefs) and in which it participates as events, is transferred in the formats indicated in objective 1 and 2 according to the type of information developed, and may also include scientific publications, interviews with experts, journalistic articles or press releases jointly with members of the cluster.

5.2.5. Results replication & exploitation

It is the subject of this report the actions of results replication and exploitation at regional level, within the cluster. Exploitation at European level is explained in the *Plan of Exploitation activities, first version D7.9* and consists mainly of Exploitation Packs for different stakeholders categories by the following KERs.

Table 2: RECONSTRUCT's preliminary identified KERs³¹

Key Exploitable Result	Type of KER	Exploitation strategy
Digital system for sourcing secondary materials		
KER1 Image processing tools	Software	SaaS subscription model
KER2 Portable HSI solution	Design	Internal use, licensing
KER3 User Interface System (UIS) decision-support tool	Software	SaaS subscription model
Circular construction materials		
KER4 AAC, AACC, and TRRC	Formulation	Direct sales, licensing
Circular construction components		

³¹ From *Plan of Exploitation activities, first version D7.9* (table 2)

KER5 Precast and Prefab elements	Design	Licensing, internal use
Digitization of material flows and digital twinning		
KER6 Digital Product Passport	Software	Licensing
KER7 BIM-based Digital Twin	Model	Licensing
KER8 RECONSTRUCT SaaS	Software	SaaS subscription model
Fully circular real-scale buildings		
KER9 Belgian Demo	Design	Freely available
KER10 Spanish Demo	Design	Freely available
Framework for circular construction		
KER11 Digital Stakeholder Platform	Software	SaaS subscription model
KER12 Regional Roadmaps	Publication	Freely available
KER14 Circular Business Models	Publication	Freely available

Analysing these KERs and other Reconstruct outputs can be detected the possible lines of replication of the developed results. At regional level, the main vias would consist of transferring the detected barriers and opinion of the sector to policy briefs, the methodologies and methods of assessment developed both in LCC, LCA, circularity & symbiosis potential and Social Assessment to standards or potential transfer to environmental certifications, incorporate the data detected in the digital flows of the project to harmonized Digital Product Passports, the employment by the sector the digital tools for design, construction, and deconstruction phases used in the project and also transfer training modules to education and skills schemes for the workforce. Other replication routes is to promote the use of the SYNER platform to generate synergies in the construction sector, to explore possible funding for the development of the digital methods, components (alternatives to Ordinary Portland Cement and manufacturing modular construction with high recycled content) or their demountable joint designs developed in the project and, promote the adoption of the CDW measuring methodologies & tools in the building sector.

Some of these paths, identified through collaborative road mapping at WP level with Reconstruct partners, are detailed in [5.7.1 Cluster activities timeline](#), being initial expectations according to the planned results of the project. New replication vias will be detected with an annual projection according to the objectives achieved in the WPs in each year (4 periods of revision of exploitation results).

5.3. Considerations on the scope and limitations of the cluster

While defining the scope, stakeholder type, digital platform and timeline of the clusters, some questions emerged that need to be asked in order to overcome and/or concretise the possible limitations and risks of the clusters. These are listed below by topic.

5.3.1. Scope

The project incorporates various topics within the broader scope of the circular economy in construction and in particular in concrete and bio-based fibre building solutions jointly with prefabricated constructions. Within this scope, several specific areas are incorporated, for example: the reduction of virgin material extraction by using recycled and reused materials, the waste reduction on site and at EoS³² by designing for deconstruction (removable prefabricated elements + ease of component separation by material for recycling or reuse), or the local industrial symbiosis. Also other areas are within the scope, as the circularity support policies, the digital technology that enable these processes assessments, the circular transition of business systems or the frameworks that define reliable indicators in circular construction. Therefore, the choice of the stakeholders that will help this transition and the scope of the clusters can be defined in a wider sense, i.e. circular economy cluster, or more specific thematic clusters within the project, such as waste cluster, cluster of concrete or prefabricated suppliers, which makes the definition of the scope more complex.

In addition, following the analysis of existing clusters at the two regional levels, several existing clusters were identified that currently encompass some of these topics but many of them in a separate way (circular economy, concrete, waste). Creating a new cluster could overlap at regional level the task currently carried out by some of them and perhaps it was a wise approach to agglutinate some clusters currently created within the Reconstruct platform to combine them (circular economy with concrete cluster and waste cluster).

From this analysis, questions arose such as: "There are circular economy clusters in general (unrealistically large), clusters of circular economy in construction, clusters of concrete, of circular concrete or of waste (recycling cluster). Could the cluster be created as an arm of another cluster (e.g. the waste cluster or concrete cluster) or a new Cluster of other related clusters? A new cluster is needed, separated from the rest of the clusters, with a more specific target of the project?". After co-creation workshop sessions, it has been deemed necessary, in light of the objectives defined in the clusters, to create a **cluster of clusters**, where different types of agents from different fields should be involved in order to reach a bigger objective in all the areas treated in Reconstruct, joining clusters that should complement each other (concrete has to be related with circular economy in construction and prefabricated cluster, for example, because all materials will ultimately have to be more circular). Thus, this cluster can be part of them as well as them being part of this cluster. This also overcomes the limitation of cluster functioning at the end of the project by

³² End of Service Life in the building cycle life

identifying the most active actors currently (within the current cluster and outside) to take over the baton of future cluster activity when the project ends.

Figure 10. Clustering in Barcelona - source: Societat Orgànica

Figure 11. Clustering in Brussels - source: Societat Orgànica

Lastly, it had to be defined whether the same type of cluster would be created in both the Barcelona and Brussels regions due to their different contexts and different solutions demonstrated in their demos. Finally, although this question will be clarified once the different types of regional stakeholders have been contacted and according to their level of interest, the clusters may differ. This is specially due to the existence of a large cluster in Brussels on circular concrete active in the region which involves a variety of actors (in contrast to Barcelona) as well as the increased use of prefabricated buildings in the region.

5.3.2. Stakeholders type

The type of stakeholders to detect and involve is related to the scope of the cluster. As mentioned above, the mapping is intended to include stakeholders from different areas related to the project as well as different types of companies, activities or those currently participating in active influential clusters. The different types are defined in the mapping of [5.5.Mapping of the local stakeholders](#) and are, for example, manufacturers of concrete, recycled aggregates, manufacturers and suppliers of prefabricated materials, companies implementing circularity in construction or waste managers, public authorities promoters, among many others. They are divided into four categories (government, research, industry and civil society), three sectors (public, private and third sector) that include diverse activities and types of company (SMEs, big companies, foundations, etc).

Questions were raised about which stakeholder types to include, for example: involving only leader companies, or on the other hand the inclusion of SMES, microenterprises or the third sector that are often left out of current influential clusters for various reasons (size, ideology, activity). The debate also arose on whether to involve only companies that currently implement or are interested in circularity in their activities or to include also companies that need this change but currently do not consider it as a guideline for their business. Finally, due to the definition of cluster adopted in this project ([4.1.Cluster Concept](#)) it was deemed necessary to include public authorities as well as private and third sector entities.

As a conclusion, SMEs, microenterprises but also leader companies in the sector as they are essential and have more influence on the implementation towards circularity in construction will be mapped and aiming at involve them. Likewise, we will seek to engage companies that currently include circularity as their priority (as experts in the field) and the ones that do not yet really consider it in their activities. Especially, we will map the latter ones, to show them that change is feasible and to introduce them to better practices than those they are currently implementing. Cluster mapping will necessarily include the private sector, which is often useful to pull the change, the third sector, which is usually the driving force and innovator in this change, as well as public entities that should be facilitators and promoters of this change for the private sector. This initial mapping will address both local and European levels.

As mentioned in [5.3.1 Scope](#), the participation of the main stakeholders of active clusters or innovative stakeholders and with the lead in circularity in the sector will be sought to ensure that, apart from achieving greater activity within the cluster, they are interested in taking over once the cluster ends within the project, without terminating the activity of this group created.

Later, once the actors that can be involved in this cluster are mapped and detected, the time and type of engagement for them will be defined, which can be different depending on the type of stakeholder.

5.3.3. Platform and activities

To support and enable the co-creation activities and the operation of the Circular Construction Clusters an online platform will be developed, to allow all the stakeholders to virtually meet and cooperate. As it happened when defining the scope of the cluster, the questions that arose were similar, such as having an own platform or including the platform inside another dynamic cluster boosting and improving their functions.

Finally it was decided to create an independent platform to facilitate the operation of the cluster and provide a repository of training materials, since current members of different clusters could be engage in Reconstruct cluster. The type of activities and functions of the platform will be defined in the next months through collaborative sessions between consortium partners and later tested by external stakeholders. The stakeholder platform and the activities to be developed for the clusters are further explained in a dedicated section under the name [5.6.Stakeholder platform](#) and [5.7.Planning activities](#).

This platform will have a temporary limitation due to domain and technical support which is planned only until the end of the project. Possible solutions have been discussed above, if we are able to involve cluster stakeholders who want to lead such groups beyond the project. They will have all the initial support already created in Reconstruct, such as this platform, its network, its functionalities and various materials included.

5.3.4. Conclusions on the scope and risks

In summary, the possible limitations that have been detected during the definition of the clusters in Reconstruct and that have been overcome, have been:

- **The concept and philosophy of a cluster** ; agreeing to use the term as understood by the CCRI and ECESP.
- **The existence of current clusters within the scope** (in Belgium above all) with the consequent danger of overloading stakeholders and overlapping information from other clusters, building alliances with members and collaborating.
- The type of **existing clusters with wide thematic areas related to circular economy**.
- The **number of clusters** related to material producers **that are not connected to the circular economy** (especially in the case of Spain), which in this case would be an advantage, to bring them together (they must be incorporated into the circular transition).
- The **broad scope of objectives addressed by Reconstruct** within the circular economy makes it difficult to define a specific scope of the cluster- looking to join various building/ materials producers' clusters under a circularity in buildings cluster, a hub of clusters.
- The **type of stakeholders and which sectors to include**, detecting the key actors within the scope defined and level of engagement expected. Also, the inclusion of different types of stakeholders: leading companies with micro-enterprises, private sector with authorities and third sector, stakeholders currently implementing circular strategies and those not yet implementing them.
- The **geographical scope** under which it will operate: territorial or national, not just local.
- How the **platform will function self-sufficiently** with the consortium, creating manuals.
- **Possible lack of coordination among the consortium & cluster** after December 2025 **when the WP7 coordination ends** and the cluster begins to run under the operation and self-coordination of each of the partners, individually. This is solved creating self-guides of platform functions and coordination manuals and, progressive transferring these independence without coordination, some months before the change. Also, quarterly **sessions** will be organised, **to plan overall actions for next months** and monitor KPIs.
- How to **make the cluster operational after the end of the project** in order to have established an initiative with interest **that can be useful beyond the time-limited intentions of the project**. For this, it is necessary to detect who has to be included, even within the consortium, in order to make it last in time.
- **Temporary limitation of the platform**: in terms of ownership and time of the domain in the cloud, management of content and operation and possible technical support in case

of malfunctions, once the project ends, although the aim is to create a self-manageable and independent stakeholder platform and supporting manuals.

- **Delayed actions.** There is a potential **risk in the formation of the cluster in the month planned** if the stakeholders are not contacted on time and the finalisation of the platform is delayed. Also, if the attractive content is not developed when starting the operation of the cluster. These interrelated **steps will be managed** within the project as time for the activity has been foreseen with sufficient safety margins.
- Challenges potentially faced when forming the clusters: There are **risks of not achieving the KPIs** set to detect the success of the clusters formed, such as **limited stakeholder engagement in the activities and results disseminated** or failure to reach target groups. This can be mitigated with a **DEC strategy prediction** that will be reviewed on a monthly basis and lead to key DEC actions such as workshops, collaboration with other R & I initiatives, stronger reliance on consortium's existing networks and the acceleration of resources to be available earlier (videos, interviews, etc). Another strategy would be **establish stakeholder attractive covenants**; like promoting their events for publicise them, providing certificates of having completed the training modules, mentions, etc

5.4. Stakeholder Mapping (regional & European)

5.4.1. Process

Once the scope, mission and objectives of the cluster have been defined and after having analysed the most relevant existing initiatives and clusters, the following steps listed in [5.1.Strategic steps for cluster formation and operation](#), are to identify the stakeholders within the scope of the cluster by carrying out a regional mapping of each region and to establish an engagement strategy to involve them which is defined in RECONSTRUCT stakeholder engagement strategy of the *Social Innovation & Circular Construction D6.1*.

1. Conduct stakeholder analysis
2. Determine stakeholders mapping within the scope defined in the clusters in Spain (mainly Catalonia) and Belgium (mainly in Flandes) as well as a European level.

In conjunction with WP6, an initial mapping of regional and European stakeholders was carried out, validated through collaborative road mapping with the consortium partners, to detect the key stakeholders in each context and identify the type of agents that were essential to incorporate.

The first step was to carry out a stakeholder mapping for all project scopes (demo sites, clusters and dissemination scope) and, secondly, to select the cluster and dissemination scope group by region, defining the level of engagement and the roles that the mapped stakeholders could play. Within these roles, stakeholders are identified in three groups: who are expected to participate in an active role inside clusters, stakeholders who can function as supporting figures and stakeholders who, with an expected more passive participating, are relevant in the dissemination of the results in the clusters at regional and European level.

Stakeholders directly related to the design and construction of the demos are outside the scope of this report, as they are analysed in the D6.1 *Social Innovation & Circular Construction*.

Figure 12. The three project scopes with different levels of stakeholder engagement - source: VUB

The next steps, after this identification of potential stakeholders to be involved in the clusters, would be their feasibility of their engagement with the cluster and once involved, agree with this initial group³³ the fundamental principles defined in this report, register and test the stakeholder platform developed to start operate as a cluster.

3. Contact & Engage key stakeholders (including policymakers) – based on priorities of engagement.
4. Kick-off and establish working groups (internal & external stakeholders involved) through engagement activities and organization of a series of meetings and workshops.
5. Test with initial group of stakeholders the Stakeholder platform once created.

5.4.2. Classification

The stakeholders identified were classified at 5 interrelated levels for each of the clusters to be established in Spain and Belgium. The stakeholder segmentation was based on:

- The "**quadruple helix**" categorisation and innovation model to include academia, industry, government, and civil society as key players in fostering collaborative innovation and sustainable development³⁴.
- Within these four big categories, they were **sub-classified by type of activity** within the sector or **field of the institution** (cement producers, precast manufacturers,

³³ External stakeholders outside the consortium

³⁴ Carayannis, E.G. and Campbell, D.F.J. (2009) "Mode 3' and 'Quadruple Helix': toward a 21st century fractal innovation ecosystem', Int. J. Technology Management, Vol. 46, Nos. 3/4, pp.201–234.

builders, promoters, professional bodies, technical institutes, certification, communication, etc.).

- For each one, we identified by colour, **the type of business** (SMEs, associations, large companies, EU projects, clusters, universities-research, etc.).
- By **geographical scope** (local, regional, national or European) within each regional context, Barcelona and Brussels.
- And by **level of expected engagement** with each stakeholder (Inform and disseminate, Consult and validate, Collaborate and co-create); in this case, inside the cluster and dissemination scope of the project.

In the following table, it is shown the sub-classification by type of activity inside the quadruple helix. These categories were presented in D7.2 and D7.9. These are used in this report for consistency throughout the project.

Table 3: RECONSTRUCT stakeholders' groups by sub-category

Stakeholder macro-groups	Stakeholders sub-category
Policymakers and public authorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European institutions and agencies • Standardisation bodies • National and local authorities
Construction value chain actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raw material suppliers • Architecture Engineering and Construction (AEC) companies • Real estate developers • Materials and components manufacturers • Logistics providers • Contractors and builders • Retrofit and renovation companies • Demolition companies • Waste management and recycling companies
Software technology developers and providers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning developers and providers • BIM and Digital Twin technology developers and providers • MAPO technology developers and providers • SaaS developers and providers
Hardware technology manufacturers and providers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Construction equipment manufacturers • Modular building component manufacturers • IoT and sensors technology suppliers • Green building technology providers
Data Management companies	
Technology service providers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IT consulting firms • Cybersecurity service providers
Financial actors and investors	Public and private investors

Clusters, associations, and interest groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU-funded projects and initiatives • Industry associations
Research & academia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research institutions and centres • Education institutions and universities • R&D departments of companies
Civil society	Building users, homeowners and renters, European citizens, NGOs
Media	Regional, national, and international media Specialised press

5.4.3. Engagement to promote participation

In order to **increase the level of stakeholder engagement in the activities and events within the cluster**, it is always intended to establish a win-win relationship to mitigate the risk of failing to reach target groups and low stakeholder engagement in the activities. This mutual agreement may be reached with each of them on an individual basis, specifying the **benefits to target stakeholders**.

Some interesting proposals considered to establish such commitment pacts are:

- It will always be desirable that in the cluster validation & co-creation participative sessions, space will be left for the needs of the stakeholders that have activities of interest for the rest of participants. Provide other needed outputs for them will be also explore.
- Its activities or events related to the cluster or to other clusters in which it participates (within the cluster scope) will also be promoted, previously agreed with consortium.
- They will be included in the participation of events allowing them to (may) have their own space to give a voice and publicity to their actions.
- They will be mentioned in the activities in which they participated in the Reconstruct project, in order to be recognised at European level.
- Support in their own objectives related with the cluster scope.
- They will be provided with free training materials relevant to their type of activity such as the training modules, as well as certificates of completion of these training programmes.
- They will be invited to discover the main outcomes of the project either through the events mentioned above or through workshops and open-labs in the demos built, to show their contribution to the sector (by the cluster participation).
- It will explain how participation in the cluster benefits each target stakeholder. For example , Reconstruct cluster benefits universities through knowledge expansion and skills development (D7.2) and inclusion of their research innovation into the Circular Systemic Solutions of CCRI, and industry clusters through the acquisition of new skills and pilot opportunities, possibility of influencing in the guidelines for circular transition in policy, technical solutions, etc. and receive support from experts in circular transition (designs, business opportunities, ...).

- Other options explored in the D6.1 *Social Innovation & Circular Construction*.

5.4.4. Stakeholder map

The first stakeholder mapping of the three project scopes with different levels of stakeholder engagement (demo sites - collaborate, clusters- consult and dissemination- inform scope) is shown in the figures below, for both regions including European stakeholders³⁵. These figures are shown in zoom detail in Annex I.

- Cluster: at this level, stakeholders are engaged to confirm assumptions or for consultation on technical details.
- Dissemination- inform: all stakeholders that should be informed about the project, even though without directly participating in development activities, should be included in this level of engagement.

The conclusions of each regional mapping are detailed in D6.1 Social Innovation & Circular Construction.

³⁵ This collaborative road map was realised jointly with consortium partners and lead by WP6. Further explanation is develop in: 3.1 *Stakeholder identification and mapping* of D6.1 *Social Innovation & Circular Construction*

STAKEHOLDER MAP BARCELONA & BRUSSELS / SPAIN & BELGIUM / EU

Figure 13: Stakeholders mapped within the 4 types of classification – Societat Orgànica, Incasòl, VUB and ICONS

From this mapping, the target stakeholders of the clusters and dissemination/exploitation, which are of interest in this report, are selected and analysed in the following sections by region (regional level) and in European level, including those selected from the mapping of CCRI members ([4.3.2 Members](#)) due to their intimate relationship with the scope of the clusters.

5.4.4.1. Barcelona – Regional level

After the conclusions of the section [5.3.2 Stakeholders type](#), in the map was included private sector actors, the third sector and public entities in different type of organisations, like SMEs, microenterprise, associations but also leader companies in the sector and those who currently include circularity as their priority (experts in the field) but also those who do not yet consider it in their activities. Regarding the type of activity they implement inside the construction sector, we provide a wide perspective of at least one actor of each activity in order to involve all the value chain in building construction. All these stakeholders are inside but also outside the consortium (external stakeholders) in the need to reach a wider audience involved. All type of stakeholders are categorised under the quadruple helix.

The list below shows the stakeholders identified in this mapping within the scope of the clusters and dissemination. In the column of level of engagement, “core” means internal stakeholders (project partners) with higher levels roles (5.5 Roles) in the cluster and directly implicated in demos of Reconstruct. “Involved” identify the external stakeholders that should be included in the cluster activities & participation and, “informed” are stakeholders with low level of engagement in the cluster but essential to disseminate to them the results obtained. The next step before establish the contact, will be the identification of the objective of engagement of each listed stakeholders through a second collaborative roadmap, now that a prevision of activities have been planned.

During the development of the project (4 years), this list could expand to a larger number of stakeholder in this or other areas of the sector that we haven't identify previously.

Table 4: Key stakeholders mapped within the scope for the cluster in Barcelona – SOO & ICONS

Segmentation (Helix)	Segmentation (Type of activity - organisation)	Geographical Scope	Level of engagement	Stakeholder
Industry	Associations	National	Involved	ANEFHOP (concrete & cement association)
Industry	Associations	National	Involved	Asociación de Centros y Servicios de Reutilización
Industry	Associations	Regional	Involved	GRCD.CAT (Chamber of Contractors)
Industry	Associations	National	Involved	Oficemen (concrete & cement association)
Industry	Building companies	National	Core	COMSA
Industry	Clusters	Regional	Involved	Cluster of waste Catalonia

Industry	Clusters	Regional	Involved	Cluster of industrialised construction
Industry	Concrete Manufacturers	National	Involved	Hercal
Industry	Concrete Manufacturers	Regional	Involved	Hormigones Montcau SA
Industry	Concrete Manufacturers Leaders	European	Involved	Lafarge-Holcim
Industry	Federations	Regional	Informed	CEPCO (Federation of Materials Producers of Catalonia)
Industry	Federations	National	Informed	CNC
Industry	Federations	Regional	Involved	FECOCAT
Industry	Prefab materials producers	Regional	Core	Soriguè
Industry	Prefab materials producers		Informed	*missing: Concrete Prefab companies leaders
Industry	Urban Miners - Deconstruction companies, waste management, recycling plants, other initiatives	Regional	Informed	Waste managers SMEs regional - list of ARC
Industry	Urban Miners - Deconstruction companies, waste management, recycling plants, other initiatives	Regional	Involved	*missing: Deconstruct companies leaders
Industry	Associations	Regional	Involved	Ciment Catala
Industry	Federations	Regional	Involved	Gremi Catalunya de prefabricats i derivats del ciment
Industry		Regional	Involved	Industries from SYM territorial projects detected
Government	European	European	Involved	ICLEI
Government	Local	Local	Involved	AMB (Barcelona Metropolitan administration)
Government	Local	Local	Informed	BIMSA
Government	Local	Local	Involved	Diputació Barcelona
Government	Local	Local	Informed	Ecologia Urbana
Government	National	National	Informed	AVS (Spanish Association of Public Managers of Housing & Land)
Government	National	National	Informed	Ministerio (CTE + RC016)
Government	Regional	Regional	Involved	ACCIÓ
Government	Regional	Regional	Involved	ARC - Catalan Waste Agency
Government	Regional	Regional	Informed	Catalan Housing Agency – Catalan agency for the management and renovation of social housing
Government	Regional	Regional	Informed	Generalitat (Ecoeficiencia)
Government	Regional	Regional	Informed	IBAVI
Government	Regional	Regional	Core	INCASOL
Government	Regional	Regional	Informed	Infraestructures.cat – Catalan agency for the development of public works

Government	Regional	Regional	Informed	Barcelona City Council
Government	Regional	Regional	Informed	Sta Perpetua de la Moguda City Council
Citizens	Associations	European	Informed	ACE-ACHE (assosiacion of structural engineers)
Citizens	Associations	Regional	Involved	CCOC- Chamber of Contractors
Citizens	Associations	Regional	Involved	Gremi de Constructors
Citizens	Blue Collar Workers	National	Involved	Construcia
Citizens	Blue Collar Workers	Regional	Involved	SaoPrat
Citizens	Communication SMEs	Regional	Involved	ANTONOMASIA SL (Andrea Sassi)
Citizens	Communication SMEs	National	Involved	Detail, L'Informatiu (construction magazines-journals)
Citizens	Federations	Regional	Informed	APCE (Catalan Association of Housing Developers)
Citizens	Professional bodies	Regional	Involved	AUS
Citizens	Professional bodies	Regional	Involved	CATEB
Citizens	Professional bodies	Regional	Involved	COAC
Citizens	Urban Miners - Deconstruction companies, waste management, recycling plants, other initiatives	National	Involved	CoCircular
Citizens	Resellers of Reclaimed Materials - building companies, public initiatives, distributors	Local	Involved	Residurecurs
Academic	SME	Regional	Core	SYM
Academic	Certifications	National	Informed	AEONOR-UNE
Academic	Certifications	National	Involved	GBce
Academic	Research Centres		Involved	Circle Economy
Academic	Research Centres	Local	Involved	Fundació Bithabitat (from Bcn Municipality)
Academic	Research Centres	European	Informed	JRC
Academic	SME	National	Core	SOO
Academic	Technical Institutions	Regional	Involved	Eurecat
Academic	Technical Institutions	Regional	Informed	IAAC (Elissabeta Carnavale?)
Academic	Associations	National	Involved	IECA (concrete & cement association) - Alejandro Josa Garcia
Academic	Technical Institutions	National	Involved	Instituto Torroja
Academic	Technical Institutions	Regional	Core	ITEC
Academic	Universities	National	Core	BUL (Brunnel)
Academic	Research Centres	Regional	Core	CTC
Academic	Universities	Local	Involved	Technical architects' Lab (Joan Ramon Rosell)
Academic	Universities	Regional	Informed	Universities (UPC, others), schools

5.4.4.2. Brussels – Regional level

The same strategies for stakeholder identification have been considered in the mapping of Belgium as in the regional context of Barcelona.

The outcomes of the collaborative road map in Belgium emphasize that, while a wide range of stakeholders can be mapped and potentially be engaged at the government, industry and academic levels, civil society (external stakeholders) is less represented in Brussel cluster. Civil society stakeholder detection will be improved during the course of the project to achieve wider range of actors of this category, which is also important for achieving the circular transition. It is highlighted that Industry holds the highest representation among stakeholders.

Moreover, the specific difference in this Flandes context is the existence of a key cluster related to circular concrete that operates in national level and which encompasses various types of sector professions and business type organisations. Brussels cluster can leverage an already established cluster, the *Living Lab Circulair Beton*³⁶, which has been promoting the adoption of circular economy practices in the local industry specially, in concrete solutions. The Living Lab will be collaborating as one of the main channel of communication with the local construction industry ecosystem. *“The objectives of engagement proved more challenging to detect. What can be inferred is that manufacturers will primarily engage in exploring new material innovations and business models. Engineering offices and contractors will serve as consultative sources for expert insights and understanding of the value chain dynamics. Finally, public authorities will be involved in policies feedbacks.”*³⁷

Figure 14: *Living Lab Circulair Beton* Cluster and some of its stakeholders & participants

In the same logic as in Barcelona, all these stakeholder could be expanded to a larger number that we haven't identify previously, during the development of the project. In the following list is shown the stakeholder mapping achieved.

³⁶ <https://vlaanderen-circulair.be/en/cases/detail/living-lab-circular-concrete>

³⁷ D6.1 *Social Innovation & Circular Construction*

Table 5: Key stakeholders mapped within the scope for the cluster in Brussels – VUB & ICONS

Stakeholder	Segmentation (Helix)	Segmentation (Type)	Geographical Scope	Level of engagement
Living Lab Circulair beton (VLAIO-project coordinated by Buildwise)	Industry	Clusters	National	Collaborate
Sweco Belgium	Industry	Engineering offices	National	Consult
ResourceFull	Industry	Engineering offices	National	Consult
AB-Roads	Industry	Engineering offices	National	Consult
DRIECON	Industry	Engineering offices	National	Consult
Betonadvies Gijko	Industry	Engineering offices	National	Consult
SBE	Industry	Engineering offices	National	Consult
Ecocem (Netherlands)	Industry	Manufacturers	National	Involve
Silmaco (Belgium)	Industry	Manufacturers	National	Involve
Holland Composites	Industry	Prefab materials producers	National	Core
Leviat (CRH group)	Industry	Manufacturers	National	Involve
Carmans	Industry	Manufacturers	National	
Gebroeders De Rycke	Industry	Manufacturers	National	
Oosterzeelse breek - en betoncentrale	Industry	Manufacturers	National	Involve
COLAS BELGIUM	Industry	Manufacturers	National	
JOZEF VANDEN BUVERIE & Co	Industry	Manufacturers	National	
Jacobs	Industry	Manufacturers	National	
AC Materials	Industry	Manufacturers	National	
Willemen Infra	Industry	Manufacturers	National	
Amacro materials of tomorrow	Industry	Manufacturers	National	
Masterbloc Gubbels	Industry	Manufacturers	National	Involve
Frangema Staal	Industry	Manufacturers	National	
Vereniging van Sloop-, ontmantelings- en Recyclagebedrijven	Industry	Federations	National	Inform
OVIO	Industry	Federations	National	Inform
Jan De Nul	Industry	Building companies	National	
Herbosch-Kiere	Industry	Building companies	National	
Aertssen Infra	Industry	Building companies	National	
Holland Composites	Industry	Manufacturers	National	
Silma-Aldrich (Merck Group)	Industry	Manufacturers	National	Involve
Marshalls nv	Industry	Manufacturers	National	
Furnibo (ARCH contact)	Industry	Contractors	National	Consult
Imerys (France)	Industry	Manufacturers	National	Involve
Embuild Vlaanderen	Industry	Federations	National	
ORI vzw	Industry	Federations	National	
RECTICEL: provider of insulating solutions	Industry	Manufacturers	National	Involve

3D weaving	Industry	Manufacturers	National	Involve
ETEX, they look for prefab concrete element solution	Industry	Manufacturers	National	Involve
FedBeton	Industry	Federations	National	Involve
DEME Infra	Industry	Building companies	National	
G&A De Meuter	Industry	Building companies	National	
Pjorre Beton	Industry	Building companies	National	
HOUBEN	Industry	Building companies	National	
Woestenborghs Bouwbedrijf	Industry	Building companies	National	
Aannemingsbedrijf Princen	Industry	Building companies	National	
Bouwbedrijf De Hauwere	Industry	Building companies	National	
Bureau Bouwtechniek	Industry	Engineering offices	National	Consult
All Belgian Recycling	Industry	Deconstruction companies, waste management, recycling plants	National	Involve
EK Recycling bv	Industry	Deconstruction companies, waste management, recycling plants	National	Inform
Besix Infra nv	Industry	Deconstruction companies, waste management	National	Inform
Grondwerken Declercq	Industry	Urban Miners - Deconstruction companies, waste management, recycling plants	National	Inform
DeVa Recycling	Industry	Deconstruction companies, waste management, recycling plants	National	Inform
Oosterzeelse breek - en betoncentrale	Industry	Urban Miners - Deconstruction companies, waste management, recycling plants	National	Involve
ACE (European Architect Council)	Industry	Federations	National	Inform
Aurubis	Industry	Manufacturers	National	Involve
Baumineral	Industry	Manufacturers	National	Involve
C-Concrete	Industry	Manufacturers	National	
Adams Polendam	Industry	Manufacturers	National	
Trans-Beton nv	Industry	Manufacturers	National	
Aannemingen Carmans	Industry	Manufacturers	National	
Van Akelyen Betoncentrale	Industry	Manufacturers	National	
Betoncentrale De Brabandere	Industry	Manufacturers	National	
Rumst Recycling	Industry	Manufacturers	National	
Devagro Beton & Recyclage	Industry	Manufacturers	National	
B-Mix Beton	Industry	Federations	National	Inform

Dubaere (rebar)	Industry	Manufacturers	National	Inform
FEBELCEM	Industry	Federations	National	Inform
GBB - BBG	Industry	Federations	National	Inform
Embuild Cobesta	Industry	Federations	National	Inform
Netwerk Architecten Vlaanderen	Industry	Federations	National	Inform
Groen Beton Vert	Industry	Federations	National	Inform
Stadsbader	Industry	Contractors	National	Consult
Baldewijns	Industry	Contractors	National	Consult
Aannemingsbedrijf Princen	Industry	Contractors	National	Consult
BESIX	Industry	Contractors	National	Consult
Airdeck	Industry	Manufacturers	National	Consult
Corvers	Industry	Contractors	National	Consult
Mourik	Industry	Contractors	National	Consult
Dekempeneer	Industry	Contractors	National	Consult
Aertssen Infra	Industry	Contractors	National	Consult
Strabag Belgium	Industry	Contractors	National	Consult
Eiffage	Industry	Contractors	National	Consult
Municipality	Government	Local	Local	Involve
Stad Gent	Government	Local	Local	Inform
Stad Mechelen	Government	Local	Local	Inform
Municipality of Asse	Government	Local	Local	Involve
Leefmilieu Brussel	Government	Regional	Regional	Inform
De Vlaamse Waterweg	Government	Regional	Regional	Inform
Facilitair bedrijf	Government	Regional	Regional	Inform
Vlaamse overheid Beleidsdomein Mobiliteit en Openbare Werken	Government	Regional	Regional	Inform
Provincie Oost-Vlaanderen	Government	Regional	Regional	Inform
Provincie West-Vlaanderen	Government	Regional	Regional	Inform
Provinciale Ontwikkelingsmaatschappij West-Vlaanderen	Government	Regional	Regional	Inform
Lantis Beheersmaatschappij Antwerpen Mobiel	Government	Regional	Regional	Inform
VLAIO Flanders innovation and entrepreneurship	Government	Regional	Regional	Inform
OVAM / Vlaanderen Circulair	Government	Regional	Regional	Inform
Buildwise - leader of the Living lab Circular Concrete	Academic	Research Centres	National	Involve
CRIC-OCCN	Academic	Research Centres	Local	Inform
ResourceFull	Academic	Research Centres	National	Inform
CERTIPRO	Academic	Certifications	National	Consult
SECO Belgium	Academic	Certifications	National	Consult
COPRO	Academic	Certifications	National	Consult
Belgische Unie voor de Technische Goedkeuring in de Bouw	Academic	Certifications	National	Consult

BE-CERT	Academic	Certifications	National	Consult
VUB	Academic	Universities	Regional	Core
Green Energy Park	Academic	Certifications	Local	Core

Finally, some of these stakeholders were identified as priority for engagement in D6.1., also specifying the level and the objectives of engagement. The list is reported in D6.1, in the table of the Annex I for Barcelona and Brussels.

5.4.4.3. CCRI members & sister projects – European level

At the European level, stakeholders within the topic scope and geographical scope of the Reconstruct regional clusters are extracted from the CCRI multi-stakeholder platform mapped and explained in section [4.4.2. Members](#) (of CCRI).

The **CCRI pilots and fellows** who have been identified as possible beneficiaries interested in the actions related to the project within the geographical scope of the future territorial clusters are the following fellows:

CCRI Cities (fellows)

- Leuven (City, Belgium) - Municipality
- Comunitat Valenciana (Region, Spain) – IVACE: Valencian Institute for Business Competitiveness

CCRI Territorial clusters

- Technological corporation of Andalusia (Territorial Cluster, Spain) - <https://www.corporaciontecnologica.com/en/>
- Metropolitan Region of Amsterdam (Territorial Cluster, Netherlands)- https://www.noord-holland.nl/English/Province_of_Noord_Holland
- Zero Waste Scotland (Territorial Cluster, United Kingdom) - <https://www.zerowastescotland.org.uk/>
- Ea éco-entreprises (Territorial Cluster, France) - <https://www.ea-ecoentreprises.com/>

The city of Leuven (City, Belgium) and the region of Comunitat Valenciana (Region, Spain) could be interesting to incorporate them as cluster members to extend the network in the government stakeholder category (which is difficult to involve) even though they are not within the same territory at local and/or regional level, of the territorial cluster of Catalonia or the one located in Brussels. They are within a national level, and these particular territories or cities coincide in similar context, language and of course CCRI objectives as in the Catalan and Flemish clusters, respectively. Regarding the selected clusters, they can help us in three of the objectives of the cluster: for further dissemination of knowledge and further stakeholders and with the expertise in the co-creation sessions of some topics within the project. Also, in the application of the replication strategies in the last year of the project.

They have been selected for sharing territorial cluster language, for their scope/thematic of action and/or for their high influence.

The **CCRI's Associate Partners** that are within the target and goal of the Reconstruct Cluster and that are interesting to contact in order to increase our connection with wider regional stakeholders and to feedback interesting initiatives for the development of the project and include they knowledge created (being three of the five objective of the clusters), are the following:

- The Commission for the Environment, Climate change and Energy (ENVE) of the European Committee of the Regions (CoR) - political representative committees (representatives that can serve to interconnect regional authorities): working on the development of the territorial pillar of the new Circular Economy Action Plan and carrying out analysis on upcoming legislative proposals to be launched by the European Commission paying particular attention to the sustainable products policy initiative, the regulation on substantiating environmental claims, the strategy on sustainable textiles, the right to repair, the packaging and packaging waste directive and the microplastics and waste reduction issues.
- Ellen MacArthur Foundation – foundation working on the circular economy transition providing knowledge, tools, expertise and active disseminator.
- European Circular Stakeholder Platform- initiative, stakeholder platform space where a large number of stakeholder and engage for different activities & events and in creating knowledge.
 - APPLiA - Home Appliance Europe, Circular Appliances: an online platform
 - MarketPlace Circular Labs (Spain & Portugal)
 - DigiCirc - Digital innovations for the Circular Economy
 - In Limbo (Brussels)
 - Ecopreneur.eu - the European Sustainable Business Federation
 - CircE Project (European regions toward Circular Economy)
 - RECIS - Circular Economy Network on Islands
 - Recovo: linking up sellers and buyers of deadstock fabric (Spain) – for the roof
 - Resourceful Cities
 - Others outside Belgium & Spain scope but in the same topics scope
- VITO – Flemish Institute for Technological Research – research institute
- European Circular Cities Declaration (ICLEI) : Local Governments for Sustainability is a global network working with more than 2500 local and regional governments committed to sustainable urban development, influencing sustainability policy and driving local action for low emission, nature-based, equitable, resilient and circular development ; through practical and integrated solutions.
- Covenant of Mayors for Climate and Energy – initiative of cities and local governments that share a long-term vision of supporting voluntary action to combat climate change.

The **CCRI's Projects** with whom we can collaborate closely due to the topics related with Reconstruct and the Circular Systemic Solutions they developed are listed below. Our work in partnership would be regarding two main objectives of the cluster being promote jointly other initiatives and campaigns and in further dissemination in European level. For that purpose, it have been coordinate a monthly assembly between the three Sister Project to develop joint strategies and aligned activities³⁸. In addition, it had been detected that, in regional level, we can coordinate also with Circ-Boost in the involvement of regional stakeholders at catalonia scope, plan joint actions in the regional cluster developed in Reconstruct and not overlapping knowledge and activities in our projects. An initial collaboration has been established and the first steps have been defined, such as collaborating in a mapping of stakeholders, avoiding overload the stakeholders. Another possibility would be the use of the stakeholder platform developed in Reconstruct for some joint activities or events with Circ-Boost, thus promoting its use and increasing its visibility. This last point is still under discussion.

- The Sister projects (Horizon Europe Cluster 4):
 - CIRC-BOOST - Boosting the uptake of circular integrated solutions in construction value chains
 - WOODCIRCLES - Integrated, Circular, and Digitally Supported Sustainable Solutions for Waste Minimization and Carbon Capture in Buildings and the Construction Sector
- Other projects in Cluster 6 but less related:
 - InvestCEC - Supporting the transition towards circular economy in European cities and regions: Development of a replicable model for local circular economy projects
 - RESOURCE – REgional project development aSsistance fOr the Uptake of an aRagonese Circular Economy
- Other projects: ReCreate, ICEBERG, HOUSEFUL, MOBICCON-PRO, CircThread, CodeDEMO, CISUFLO, NewWave, RECONMATIC, BIO4EEB, EASY ZERO, DESIRE, BEST, RECOMPOSE

Moreover, Reconstruct will actively collaborate with and participate in events, workshops and activities organised by the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI).

³⁸ To kick off and facilitate this collaboration, the cluster has applied for the Horizon Results Booster services Module A and Module B, aiming at supporting the Cluster's joint dissemination activities. First, a portfolio of research and innovation results will be created (D1.1, mod A) aiming to better identify the commonalities of the cluster members in terms of results and stakeholders. Then, a joint dissemination strategy will be developed and implemented, with the support of the HRB Experts team. In addition, Cluster joint dissemination materials (such as a video and factsheet) will be created by the HRB. – *Plan of the Dissemination and Communication activities - 1st version/D7.2*

5.4.4.4. Outside CCRI – European level

Outside CCRI but in European level, has been detected some initiatives that would be common in both clusters for the objective that needs larger level of implementation. These are listed below:

Table 6: Key stakeholders mapped within the scope for clustering, at EU level

Stakeholder	Segmentation (Helix)	Segmentation (Type)	Geographical Scope	Level of engagement
Fellows and pilots from CCRI	Government	Regional	European	Collaborate
Social Housing EU	Government	European	European	Inform
ICONS	Citizens	Communication SMEs	European	Core
ACE (European Architect Council)	Citizens	Associations	European	Inform
BUL (Brunnel)	Academic	Universities	National	Core
Arup	Academic	SME	European	Involve
European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform	Academic	Eu initiatives	European	Involve
Sister projects: WoodCircles, CIRC-BOOST	Academic	Eu initiatives	European	Collaborate
CCRI's Associate Partners - initiatives	Academic	Eu initiatives	European	Inform
JRC	Academic	Research Centres	European	Consult

5.5. Roles

Leadership, membership, governance

- **Manager and Coordinator:** Societat Orgànica is responsible for coordinating cluster activities. Incasòl is the institution responsible for managing cluster activities in Barcelona regional cluster. Green Energy Park and VUB are the managers for cluster activities in Brussels regional cluster.
- **Membership and Stakeholders:** diverse representation within the specific target of the building sector covering all needed roles and profiles to achieve the objectives. They are mapped in 5.4 Stakeholder Mapping and the next step will be to engage them into the cluster to define this point.
- **Working groups:** they will be divided by type of activity inside the construction sector to help establish the cocreation sessions that are focused on specific topics. They are mapped in 5.4 Stakeholder Mapping and will depend on the engagement of each stakeholder (level of engagement).

The actions or session in each working group has to be led by a project partner who have expertise or interest (leader of a task or WP) in conducting the session, and with the help of the rest of the consortium, carries it out. These responsibilities are shown in

the following diagram of the internal roles in the Reconstruct clusters and with CCRI. Roles from external stakeholders will be defined in participative session with them like workshops, once involved, which are planned during May 2024 to September, just prior to the establishment of clusters in October 2024.

Figure 15. Roles in Clusters by Reconstruct partners - source: Societat Orgànica.

The training, co-creation or validation activities with the cluster stakeholders along with the promotion of other regional events and initiatives and the encouragement of cluster members' participation in the organised events will be led by a partner at regional level for each cluster, who understand the specific context. They will be assisted by the other partners. These regional leaders, Incasol and Green Energy Park, will be the organisers and managers of the activities, although they will be driven and proposed by the partners interested in developing a specific activity with the stakeholders. In the case of Incasol, it is a recognised public authority that is aware of the regional reality and context and is therefore a natural leader in this task. In the case of Green Energy Park, as it belongs to the academia,

it will be helped by the rest of the Brussels partners who have more relations and experience with other types of actors such as industry or the public sector.

On the other hand, ITEC is responsible for the design of the training modules and the management of their creation, but the development of the content to be incorporated in the training modules is a task of all the partners of the project according to the topic of the module (related to each WP) as well as the content of the proposed events. The training modules will be adapted to European level also by them, although their dissemination and coordination towards European organisations or the CCRI will be handled by ICONS.

The communication, dissemination and exploitation of the cluster (and project) results will be managed by ICONS. ICONS will participate directly in the European dissemination with CCRI but indirectly in the cluster dissemination, which will be done through the regional cluster leaders (INC & GEP), in order to detect local interest. IRIS will have the lead in developing virtual spaces and modules within the Stakeholder platform, that the cluster and its members will use to participate in all activities and dispose of the training materials.

The stakeholder contact and engagement will be led by ICONS. ICONS will need the support of regional partners of each cluster to:

- i. understand the context of each region,
- ii. identify the stakeholders that need to be involved as a priority;
- iii. and the approach to start a collaboration with them, according to each cluster.

For Barcelona cluster ITEC, SOO, INC, COM, SOR and CTC will be involved and, for Brussels cluster VUB, HOL and GEP. Finally, to supervise the correct operation and manage the coordination between all the actions and those in charge, Societat Orgánica will be responsible for the coordination of activities between the two clusters' interaction at the regional level in close cooperation with the CCRI-CSO and the other sister projects at the European level, with ICONS support. Societat Orgánica will also support the co-creation of the cluster from the viewpoint of methodology as it is shown in this Cluster Action Plan report.

Furthermore, the relationship between internal project tasks directly involved in the formation and coordination of the clusters, in WP7, are shown below. These are also directly related to the roles defined above.

Figure 16. Project tasks directly involved in the formation and coordination of the clusters in WP7 - source: Societat Orgànica

5.6. Stakeholder platform

Infrastructure, resources and functionality

- Physical or virtual infrastructure: Virtual platform will be create to hold virtual meetings and organize face to face events in avalabile spaces or shared facilities, facilitating collaboration and knowledge exchange.
- Financial resources: The funding of this platform and cluster operation is inside the Reconstruct project, under the funding of the European Research Executive Agency (REA) through the Project: 101082265 — RECONSTRUCT — HORIZON-CL6-2022-CIRCBIO-02-two-stage. Derived via consortium partners.

To support and enable the co-creation activities and the operation of the Circular Construction Clusters will be developed a virtual platform (cloud solution) where all the stakeholders would meet and cooperate and where will be provided a repository of training materials and replication packs in a dedicated module. Also, the platform will support the dissemination and exploitation activities of the project.

The services and functionalities of the platform will be defined in T7.2, based on the cluster objectives and activities and user requirements, before May 2024 through collaboration sessions between relevant consortium partners involved in the clusters. From May 2024 to January 2025, the platform will be developed and a first version will be launched. During February and April 2025, this version will be tested by internal and also external stakeholders to address new user needs that may appear, improve the intuitive functions and finally integrate the set of micro-services and modules needed to operate within the cluster. The platform will use IRIS proprietary platform-building framework (MOAP). Upon completion of the latest version in April 2025, the platform will function autonomously where new stakeholder registrations will be made automatically and will be used for all sets of activities defined in the cluster without the need for technical support.

Within the private space, different modules will be incorporated to support the objectives set in the cluster, mainly hosting the training modules, the exploitation packs and the outcomes of the co-creation sessions of the four main topics. Another part of the platform will be the promotion of the events and workshops organised at regional level and other initiatives of cluster members who are interested in giving themselves visibility in aspects related to the scope of the cluster. It will also incorporate functionalities that allow collaboration at two scales between stakeholders, such as the possibility of running online meetings / webinars or internal chat and posts. It will define which functions will be incorporated within the platform and which are exclusive to the Reconstruct website in terms of dissemination or promotion of external events. European level events and dissemination will be outside the platform and will be made via the website, referring stakeholders to it as they are not functions directly related to the cluster.

Finally, it will work on the possibility of the Post project exploitation of the platform (domain, property), to allow strengthening the work done as its network, its functionalities and its repository like the training materials created.

5.7. Planning activities

Research, innovation, training

- Participative activities: regular meetings, workshops, webinars, events and networking to facilitate collaboration addressed to key challenges and best practices in circularity in construction.

- Technology transfer: a series of technology solutions will be created within the project, such as: Image processing tools (Software), Portable HSI³⁹ solution design, User Interface System (UIS) decision-support tool, circular assessments & symbiosis potential methodologies and Digital Stakeholder Platform. Also a series of technical solutions like AAC⁴⁰ (material), removable prefabricated AACC⁴¹ façade panels with recycled aggregates, recycled exterior pavement and modular TRRC⁴² sandwich panels. There is an objective to promote the adoption of some of these solutions in the building sector.
- Skills development: a training program to steer professionals through all the common challenges faced in circular construction will be developed. It will be adaptable to different profiles of professionals in the construction sector.

The activities carried out within the cluster will promote participation and help us to meet the cluster's objectives. In the following section, the most appropriate activities to achieve each objective are analysed and the choice of each will depend on the profile of the stakeholder group and the specific topic in which participation is required. The type of activities analysed are mainly digital and, in some cases, face-to-face; in a variety of formats and duration, ensuring their transmission in an effective, responsive, practical and useful way to the stakeholders involved.

In section 5.1.1. Organisation Timeline (main steps), the planned activities are distributed in time, establishing a temporal approximation of the first intuitions in this stage of the project prior to the establishment of the clusters, which may be modified according to the course of the project and the stakeholders that could be involved. Once the timeline of the activities has been defined and the cluster has been formed, it will be validated with the CCRI Coordination and Support Office (CCRI-CSO) to be aligned with the TWG needs. The activities organised will be agreed upon with the CCRI Coordination and Support Office (CCRI-CSO), aiming at identifying cooperation & partnership and knowledge exchanges while avoiding overlaps with CCRI members and sister EU projects under the same topic within Horizon Europe Cluster.

Also, the project will regularly participate in CCRI activities – for instance the thematic working group meetings, webinars, workshops and/or biannual CCRI conferences. Similarly, the participation of the CCRI CSO in project activities will be envisaged when relevant.

The participation in the activities will be realised with external stakeholders and internal stakeholders, both members of clusters, although the organisation of these activities will be mainly managed by the internal stakeholders (of the project). The profile of each working group created for these participatory activities will depend on the thematic and stakeholder engagement.

³⁹ HyperSpectral Imaging

⁴⁰ Alkali activated cement

⁴¹ Alkali-activated cement-based concrete

⁴² Textile Reinforced Recycled Concrete

Objective 1: Generate knowledge

The target audience for this objective will be stakeholders external to the project and the activities will be created mainly by the project consortium during the development of the project.

Table 7: Actions and Activities planned in Objective 1 within the cluster

Activity	Format	Duration	Scope	Location	KPI
Creation of Training modules	-Video clips (webinars,tutorials, experts' interviews) - Presentations (ppt) - Questionarios & gamificación	To be defined. Expected to be short with formats < 45min each one.	Each module will be thematic specific	Stakeholder platform (SP) – Dedicated module	One training module per WP. Audience profile would be define in T7.6
Shared Materials and outcomes developed in WPs	-Guidelines & handbooks - Project outcomes presentations - Summary of cluster members participation sessions reports - Webinars	No restriction. Depending on the WP outputs	Each WP is thematic specific	Stakeholder platform - repository	None
Shared Materials from other activities where knowledge has been generated (workshops, openlabs, events).	- Recordings of events or workshops (if streaming) - Summary report and graphic information from events, open-labs and workshops	No restriction. Depending on the activity carried out.	Events could be more general topics. Open-labs would be demo specific	Reconstruct Website (including link in SP)	None
Scientific publications	- Scientific publications	Depending on the publication	KERs of Reconstruct	Scientific magazines	At least 3
Policy briefs	- Reports	No restriction.			-
Create an Innovation handbook	- Handbook	No restriction	Summary of Reconstruct outcomes	Reconstruct Website	1 at the end of the project

Objective 2: Stakeholders participation, co-creation & validation

All these activities are carried out through the Stakeholder Platform. The target audience will be both external and internal stakeholders from the cluster. The sessions will be organised according to the roles specified in the cluster (5.5. Roles). In the case of events

and openlabs, they are specified in the Dissemination and Communication Plan - 1st version/D7.2.

Table 8: Actions and Activities planned in Objective 2 within the cluster

Activity		Format	Duration	Scope
Co-creation session: to co-create the clusters' foundational principles	- Meetings (only consortium partners)	- Digital meetings - Oral presentations & graphic information	3 meetings around 1 h	Cluster topics: Foundational principles
Co-creation session: discussions and feedback about key areas to transitate to circular buildings	- Workshop (groupal) - Focus group (groupal) - Event + round table (groupal)	- Digital meetings & presentations through Stakeholder platform - Mainly digital events	To be defined. Expected to be meetings <1:30h	Big topics: EU policy, technical solutions and business models transition, digital data and assessments.
Consultation session (asking for): stakeholder consultation for inputs	- Survey - Live interview (individual) - Workshop (groupal) - Focus group (groupal)	- Digital survey by email - Digital meetings & presentations through Stakeholder platform	To be defined. Expected to be meetings < 1 h	Each Task & WP is thematic specific
Validation session: validation of the inputs previously considered by the consortium or of the outputs achieved	- Survey - Live interview (individual) - Workshop (groupal) - Focus group (groupal) - Event + round table (groupal)	- Digital survey by email - Digital meetings & presentations through Stakeholder platform - Digital or Face-to-face events	To be defined. Expected to be meetings <1:30h	Each Task & WP is thematic specific
Open-labs at demo sites	- Open-labs	- Face-to-face lab - Workshops	Diverse. 3 labs in each demo.	Demo specific topic
Final event	- Event (digital or face-to-face)	- Presentations - Debates	To be defined. 1 event.	Reconstruct topics

Objective 3: Promote other initiatives

Initiatives will be promoted both from the cluster members and from external initiatives related to the scope of the cluster and also participation in these events is encourage. Mainly, CCRI events will be promoted.

Table 9: Actions and Activities planned in Objective 3 within the cluster

Activity		Format	Duration	Scope
Promote or participate CCRI Events (from CCRI stakeholders or CCRI-CSO) ⁴³	- Event (digital or face-to-face) - Workshops - Roundtables	- Meetings & presentations - Debates	Diverse	Of interest for the cluster
Promote cluster stakeholders events and other third parties	- Event (digital or face-to-face) - Workshops - Roundtables	- Meetings & presentations - Debates	Diverse	Of interest for the cluster
Joint events (Sister & CCRI)	- Meetings - Social campaigns - Events	- Digital meetings & presentations - Videos - Reports	Diverse 3 joint events	Big topics
Participate in cluster stakeholder events and/or involve cluster stakeholders in Reconstruct events.	- Event (digital or face-to-face) - Workshops - Roundtables	- Meetings & presentations - Debates	Diverse	Of interest for the cluster
Webinars & workshops organized in conjunction with big sectorial events or CCRI	- Webinars - Workshop - Events	- Presentations - Debates	Diverse 4 webinars / workshops	Diverse
Promote companies with best practices (from the cluster or others such as CCRI)	To be defined	To be defined	Short and direct	Of interest for the project

Objective 4: Communication & dissemination

The communication and dissemination of the project will be done through the website, social media (Twitter, LinkedIn), E-newsletter sent by Reconstruct as well as through other media multipliers (such as press or scientific magazines) and partner corporate websites as explained in the *Dissemination and Communication Plan D7.2*. In the case of clusters, the information to be disseminated will mainly be that created in the cluster through stakeholder co-creation sessions or the organisation of or attendance at events related to Reconstruct

⁴³ Calendars of events within the scope: <https://circular-cities-and-regions.ec.europa.eu/events> & <https://horizoneuropencppportal.eu/ncp-networks/cluster-4/calendar> con los sites project. Contact to add to the CCRI calendar the proposed circular economy event organised: helpdesk@circular-cities-and-regions.eu

topics. In addition, journalistic articles or joint press releases can be planned with partners from the cluster or the CCRI.

Objective 5: Results replication & exploitation

It is identified the activities that could be carried out to explore the possibility of the results obtained being adopted by the cluster's stakeholders and thus leverage on the components, tools or methodologies developed during the project.

Table 10: Actions and Activities planned in Objective 5 within the cluster

Activity	Format	Scope
Adoption of the Policy briefs reported	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Interviews (individual) - Focus group (groupal) - Face-to-face Events 	Regulations, protocols and standards
Explore possible funding for the development of the components design to market it	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Interviews (individual) - Demostrative events - Open-lab - Advertising brochure 	Removable Façade panels
Exploitation sessions of the assesments methodologies developed in Reconstruct - potential transfer to environmental certifications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Interviews (individual) - Webinars - Reports 	digital methods, componentes, medicion de CDW, syner platform, training programmes
Identification of stakeholders interested in the application of the digital tools used in the project.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Events - Focus group (groupal) - Webinars - Questionnaires 	Digital tools
Promote the use of the SYNER platform to generate synergies in the construction sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Focus group (groupal) - Events 	SYNER - Simbiosis potential
Promote the adoption of the CDW measuring methodologies & tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Interviews (individual) - Focus group (groupal) 	CDW management

5.7.1. Start to operate with the cluster - Cluster activities Timeline

A collaborative road mapping with consortium partners was designed in T6.1 to understand the research agenda at the WP level in the three level of engagement identified: demonstration, cluster and dissemination. With this first approach to the validation sessions and together with some of the events identified in advance, an initial timeline of these activities is made, which will be updated throughout the project with activities also agreed with the cluster members. This timeline should be considered as a first version that shows the activities that have been temporarily planned up to now, but never as definitive.

Figure 17. Cluster planned activities timeline Months 1 to 12 (1st version) - Societat Orgànica & WP leaders

Figure 18. Cluster planned activities timeline Months 13 to 24 (1st version) - Societat Orgànica & WP leaders

It is shown until month 24, as an example. These activities are included in Miro Board to able updates by partners, as a working tool.

6. Monitoring and evaluation of the Cluster Action Plan

As an initial step for the formation of the cluster, the Cluster Action Plan has been defined, outlining the framework for the upcoming activities and including a timetable highlighting the short, medium and long term priorities. In order to verify the acquisition of the objectives and to verify their implementation, impact and success, a Monitoring and Evaluation plan must be defined to assess the key performance indicators⁴⁴ and the methodology for their detection. The Monitoring and Evaluation Plan will serve to mitigate possible risks in the clusters's functioning like the limited engagement of stakeholders in cluster's activities and results, content and activities created with limited relevance to the target audience or low social acceptance of the results generated. High acceptance is vital for market adoption of the project's solutions.

6.1. Monitoring and adjustment of the Cluster Action Plan

Monitoring and adjusting the plan involves several steps to ensure that the project stays on track and adapts to changing circumstances. The following eight steps will act as a guide on how to do this effectively. Flexibility, clear communication, and a proactive approach to problem-solving are key elements of effective plan management⁴⁵.

Monitoring, evaluation, plan adjustment

1. Performance metrics: To evaluate and monitor the final objectives and participation pursued in the success of the Regional Cluster formation, **Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)** have been defined.

- >40 Clustermembers
- 200 platform users
- % of activity objectives achieved
- No. of transfer activities carried out

2. Monitoring system: to regularly collect data on the determined KPIs using the stakeholder's platform and data recording tools.

⁴⁴ ECCP, 2021: Guide on Capacity Building for Clusters, European Cluster Collaboration Platform: https://clustercollaboration.eu/sites/default/files/news_attachment/Guide%20on%20Capacity%20Building%20for%20Clusters.pdf on 20th March 2024.

⁴⁵ SARAH, 2024: A Comprehensive Guide to Cluster Analysis: Applications, Best Practices and Resources recovered from <https://www.displayr.com/understanding-cluster-analysis-a-comprehensive-guide/> on 20^o march 2024.

The stakeholder platform will have a system for analysing the interactions carried out, which will make it possible to evaluate them in terms of number but also by type. This will make it possible to know the number of users, attendance at online activities and, through surveys, the level of satisfaction achieved in the transfer activities.

3. Regular evaluation: by regular meetings to evaluate the plan development involving project managers and relevant stakeholders.

These KPIs will be reviewed and monitored during the development of the Cluster Plan and, ultimately, some action will be taken if they are not being achieved, identifying the areas for improvement. These regular evaluations of the KPIs achieved will be conducted every 6 months.

4. Comparison of actual and planned progress: to identify any discrepancies or areas where adjustments may be necessary.

The provision of data on the fulfilment of the key indicators of the action plan will be complemented by the qualitative assessment to be carried out by the actors responsible for each partner involved in the tasks. Both quantitative and qualitative evaluations will make it possible to establish the level of compliance with the plan's expectations and to define the measures that may need to be implemented to adjust them.

5. Risks assessment: in addition to the mentioned limited engagement of the stakeholders this could include delays and resource constraints.

The quantitative and qualitative analysis described in the previous point will make it possible to determine, in front of situations of non-compliance with the objectives set for the different key indicators, whether there are risks that could become barriers to the achievement of the plan. If such barriers or risks are detected, they must be notified to the persons responsible for the tasks and the work package as well as to the project leader for their consideration.

6. Adjust the plan: this could involve revising timelines, reallocating resources, reprogramming activities or revising plan scopes.

One of the main aspects to be taken into account for the success of the plan is the development of the planned activities within the given timeframe. The point [5.1.1 Organisational timeline](#) of the same document sets out the timing of the phases of stakeholder engagement, cluster establishment, digital platform development and cluster activities. The first and fourth of these activities depend to a large extent on how much stakeholders are involved and, as mentioned above, this is one of the risks identified and could lead to changes in the plan. The second and third activities (establishment of the cluster and development of the digital platform) are more dependent on the project partners and are therefore not where possible adjustments to the plan are foreseen.

In addition, it is set out the initial prevision of the planned participative actions and activities before and during the cluster functioning in section [5.7.1 Cluster activities timeline](#). In this

way it is possible to foresee the adjustment of the activities plan, modifying activities or including new ones of major interest.

7. Communicate changes: ensure that all stakeholders are informed about any changes made to the Action Plan.

The plan's own instruments, i.e. the cluster itself and its supporting digital platform, will be used to share with users the modifications that may be adopted. This communication will not only work in the sender-receiver sense, but will also contemplate iteration, through consultations or meetings that facilitate taking into account the opinions, preferences and availability of stakeholders.

8. Document adjustments: to keep detailed records of all changes made to the Action Plan, as well as the reasoning behind those changes.

For the registration of modifications to the Cluster Action Plan, the documentary and communication systems foreseen in the project will be used. These include, in particular, the following ones.

- new documents based on this report
- a specific document on plan activities
- the digital platform for stakeholders
- other cluster's communication resources

6.2. Evaluation of Cluster Action Plan implementation

Evaluating the plan implementation involves assessing various aspects of the plan's execution and its impact on the intended goals⁴⁶. The following seven steps summarise the process of evaluating and drawing conclusions about the implemented plan.

1. Recover metrics information on objectives, KPIs and data collection of the Cluster Action Plan in order to map its development, results and observations made during its operation. This information is the basis for the assessment steps and conclusions that follow.

2. Performance measurement: the data and feedback collected shall be analysed to measure the results of the implementation of the plan against the previously established parameters and, where appropriate, those that have been modified.

3 Stakeholder feedback: the different parties involved in the development of the plan will be consulted, including the different stakeholder profiles and representatives of participating entities, governmental bodies and also project partners. Their satisfaction levels, their

⁴⁶ GIZ, 2020: Cluster Development Guide, Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) GmbH, recovered from <https://www.giz.de/en/downloads/giz2021-en-cluster-development-guide.pdf> on 20th March 2024.

perception of the effectiveness of the plan, their opinions and any suggestions for improvement will be assessed.

4. Compliance check: this phase aims to ensure that the implementation of the plan, more specifically of the validated and transferred knowledge and innovations, is in compliance with the relevant regulations, codes and standards of the construction sector at European level. Or, if this is not the case, it shall be ensured that assumptions or proposals for changes to them have been considered. It shall also be assessed whether cluster developments meet the specified requirements and contribute to achieving the objectives of the plan.

5. Cost-benefit analysis: a cost-benefit analysis will be carried out to assess the economic feasibility and effectiveness of the implementation of the plan. Comparison of the costs and also of the efforts associated with the implementation of the plan with the benefits and other results obtained will make it possible to draw conclusions and recommendations useful in the drafting of similar plans in the future.

6. Community impact assessment: it is also important to assess the impact of the scheme on the local community, i.e. in the specific areas of the Barcelona and Brussels regions, including the social, economic and environmental aspects of the knowledge transferred. The evaluation should verify whether the Cluster Action Plan has contributed to the enhancement of the relationship between stakeholders, to the continuity of the cluster or its activities after the end of the project, to the effective enhancement of the circular management of resources and other positive results expected or derived from the functioning of both clusters.

7. Documentation and reporting: the evaluation process, conclusions and recommendations must also be documented in a report. This document will be presented to interested parties and participating entities and also to the decision makers who have been detected as key actors in the sector. The objective is to communicate the results of the implementation of the plan and facilitate transparency and accountability.

6.3. Next steps for cluster establishment

In the coming months, as has been seen along this document, it is proposed to continue to attend the annual and 6-monthly assemblies of each working group as well as to carry out all the cluster's objectives.

The following first activities of the Cluster Action Plan will be carried out over the next six months.

1. Engagement and stakeholder contact
2. Meetings with initial groups – establishment of the cluster and engagement
3. Testing of the platform and stakeholder's registration
4. Registration of the Barcelona and Brussels clusters in CCRI
5. Start of activities within the cluster- Kick-off

6. Follow-up and monitoring of activities

1. Engagement and stakeholder contact

Engagement and networking thrive on synergy and collaboration among diverse stakeholders (see [5.4 Stakeholder Mapping](#)), with each party bringing its unique perspectives, resources and expertise to foster meaningful connections and drive positive outcomes⁴⁷.

This engagement strategy for potential stakeholders is defined in D6.1 *Social Innovation & Circular Construction*. As part of the cluster action plan, the external stakeholders' expectations will be assessed through a survey, in collaboration with WP7. This entails setting the baseline for the monitoring process as they will be asked about their place in the transition curve (e.g. whether they are already experts in digital workflows), their interests in Reconstruct's main research topics (e.g. material innovation, digital workflow etc.) and preferred level of engagement. External stakeholders will also receive an overview of what to expect in the coming years, based on the cluster action plan. Both stakeholders' expectations and acceptance will feed into D6.2. Roadmaps allow different stakeholder groups of Reconstruct to see the bigger picture and understand how their contributions fit into the broad vision of the project (Kerr et al., 2017).

The technology and communication platforms envisaged in the Cluster Action Plan will facilitate engagement in the way described at [5.4.3. Engagement to promote participation](#). These tools will provide the infrastructure to connect stakeholders, disseminate information and foster dialogue. However, it is also important to maintain personal contact and generate activities that do not involve the permanent use of computing devices, to avoid digital saturation.

Based on the stakeholder maps of the Barcelona and Brussels regions, the process started with the stakeholder mapping lead by Icons and relevant regional partners. Once the invitation to participate from each cluster has been formulated and the willingness of each stakeholder is known, the registration on the platform and the participation in the kick-off event will take place. Thereafter, stakeholders who wish to continue with the activities will participate in the activities as described in 5.7.

Follow the engagement of stakeholders to strengthen the network.

3. Testing of the platform and stakeholder's registration

The stakeholder's platform described at [5.6](#) should be tested before starting the registration process. Testing a digital platform for building users involves a series of steps to ensure its capabilities and functionalities.

⁴⁷ CCRI, 2021: Methodology for the implementation of a circular economy at the local and regional scale, Circular Cities and Regions Initiative, 2021, recovered from <https://circular-cities-and-regions.ec.europa.eu/support-materials/ccri-documents/methodology-implementation-circular-economy-local-and-regional> on 20th March 2024.

1. Usability: evaluate the user interface for ease of navigation, intuitiveness, and overall user experience.
2. Compatibility: test the platform across different devices (desktops, laptops, tablets, smartphones) and browsers (Chrome, Firefox, Safari, Edge).
3. Security: perform vulnerability assessment and penetration testing, test for common security issues.
4. Accessibility: verify that the platform complies with accessibility standards, screen reader compatibility, keyboard navigation, and color contrast.
5. Documentation and training: review and update user documentation, tutorials, and help guides, conduct training sessions for users.
6. User acceptance: ask real users or stakeholders in UAT to validate that the platform meets their expectations.
7. Deployment: plan and execute a smooth deployment strategy to roll out the platform to users.

4. Registration of the Barcelona and Brussels clusters in CCRI

In order to obtain the registration of the Barcelona and Brussels clusters in the CCRI - Circular Cities and Regions Initiative, the following steps must be followed:

1. Contact the Initiative (this step has already been taken): several members of the Reconstruct project are already part of the CCRI community, participating in its activities, regularly consulting the website, receiving the newsletter and being in contact with CCRI representatives.
2. Submit registration information: provide the necessary information about each cluster when prompted. This might include details such as the participating regions, the scope of their circular economy activities, any ongoing activities, and their goals.
3. Engage and collaborate: once the two clusters are registered, actively engage with the initiative and collaborate with other clusters and stakeholders (this step has already been initiated outside the regional cluster, but in the Sister Project clustering). Participate in events, share best practices, and contribute to the overall objectives of the circular economy.

5. Start of activities within the cluster

Starting activities cluster with a kick-off event should be an effective way to generate enthusiasm, engage stakeholders, and set the tone for collaboration and innovation. This shall take account of the following aspects.

4. Plan of activities: type and scope, overview of the cluster's purpose and goals, interactive activities or workshops to encourage engagement and participation
5. Event logistics: suitable venue, virtual or hybrid format, date and time, necessary equipment and facilities.

6. Compelling agenda: key activities, welcome and introductions, presentations on relevant topics, panel discussions, networking opportunities for participants to connect and collaborate
7. Invite participants: all relevant stakeholders, clearly communicate the purpose of the event, its agenda, and any logistical details.
8. Promote the event: by using the stakeholder's platform and other communication channels (email newsletters, social media platforms, industry forums...).
9. Prepare presentations: presentations, handouts, and other materials that will be used during the kick-off event and the following activities.
10. Facilitate engagement and interaction: design to encourage active participation and interaction among attendees with group discussions, brainstorming sessions, etc.
11. Capture feedback and next steps: feedback from participants to gauge their impressions and gather suggestions for future activities.

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9. Annex II

Working group	Activity type	Cluster objective	Objective of engagement	Commitment agreement
Working group 1				
Working group 2				
Working group x				

Figure 19: Next steps: define the working groups to match the stakeholders with the activities planned. Template model.

